

ATMO ACCESS

Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Title	Third report with feedback from users and statistics on use of the services
Work package n°	10
Deliverable n°	10.6
Lead beneficiary	NILU
Author(s)	Lise Eder Murberg (NILU), Damien Boulanger (CNRS), Ute Karstens (ICOS), Alex Vermeulen (ICOS), Véronique Riffault (IMT), Antonia Zogka (CNRS/IMT)
Deliverable Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Estimated delivery date	M53
Actual delivery date	M54
Version	V2 (updated on 18.03.2026)
Reviewed by	Ulrich Bundke (FZJ), Ariane Dubost (Project Office, CNRS)
Accepted by	
Comments	<p>V1: This deliverable was submitted with a one-month delay to include latest data from the virtual training (including serious game)</p> <p>V2: Following the final external review, the deliverable was corrected according to the recommendations.</p>

Table of contents

1	Summary and highlights	5
2	Introduction	6
3	Usage metrics	7
4	Virtual Access Portal	10
4.1	Updates throughout the project	11
4.2	Statistics on use of the online services	11
4.2.1	User activity on the VA portal	12
4.2.2	Service access via the VA portal	13
4.3	Feedback from the general feedback form	14
5	ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal	16
5.1	Updates throughout the project	18
5.2	Statistics on use of the Homeless Data Portal	20
5.2.1	Users' activity on the Homeless Data Portal	20
5.2.2	Data requests through the Homeless Data Portal	22
5.3	Feedback from users on the Homeless Data Portal	23
5.3.1	User panel for Homeless Data Portal	23
5.3.2	Feedback form for the Homeless Data Portal	23
6	Time Series Analysis	27
6.1	Updates throughout the project	28
6.2	Statistics on use of the Time Series Analysis service	29
6.2.1	Usage metrics for the Time Series Analysis service	29
6.2.2	Data analysis requests in the Time Series Analysis Service	30
6.3	Feedback from users on the Time Series Analysis service	31
6.3.1	User panel for Time Series Analysis service	31
6.3.2	Feedback form for the Time Series Analysis service	32
7	ACTRIS footprint analysis service for aerosol and trace gas measurements	35
7.1	Updates throughout the project	38
7.2	Statistics on use of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service	39
7.2.1	Usage metrics for the ACTRIS footprint analysis service	40
7.2.2	Model requests in the ACTRIS footprint analysis service	41

7.2.3	Scientific papers	44
7.3	Feedback from users on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service	46
7.3.1	User panel on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service	46
7.3.2	Response on feedback form related to ACTRIS footprint analysis.....	46
8	<i>ICOS Footprint analysis service for greenhouse gases.....</i>	50
8.1	Updates throughout the project	52
8.2	Statistics on use of the ICOS footprint analysis service	54
8.2.1	Usage Metrics for the ICOS Footprint Viewer	54
8.2.2	Model requests for the ICOS Footprint Service	56
8.2.3	Model results downloaded for the ICOS Footprint Service.....	57
8.2.4	Scientific papers.....	58
8.3	Feedback from users on the ICOS footprint analysis.....	59
8.3.1	User panel on the ICOS footprint analysis	59
8.3.2	Response on feedback form related to ICOS footprint analysis.....	60
9	<i>IAGOS Footprint analysis service for tropospheric vertical profiles</i>	63
9.1	Updates throughout the project	64
9.2	Statistics on use of the IAGOS footprint analysis service.....	65
9.2.1	Usage metrics for the IAGOS footprint analysis service	65
9.2.2	Model visualization requests for the IAGOS footprint analysis service	66
9.3	Feedback from users on the IAGOS footprint analysis service.....	67
9.3.1	User panel on the IAGOS footprint analysis	67
9.3.2	Response on feedback form related to the IAGOS footprint analysis service.....	68
10	<i>Online training services.....</i>	68
10.1	Massive Open Online Course (MOOC).....	69
10.1.1	Description of service	69
10.1.2	Response on feedback form related to MOOC through the ATMO-ACCESS portal	69
10.1.3	Number of participants and global reach	70
10.1.4	Participants' level of education and gender/age diversity	71
10.1.5	Audience attraction and scientific background	73
10.1.6	Visibility	75
10.1.7	Completion rates	75
10.1.8	User feedback.....	76
10.2	Tutorial videos	79
10.2.1	Description of service	79
10.2.2	Usage metrics	80

10.2.3	User feedback and survey analysis	81
10.3	Serious game	86
10.3.1	Description of service	86
10.3.2	Usage metrics.....	86
10.3.3	User feedback and survey analysis	86
11	Conclusion and next steps.....	89
12	Appendix: General Feedback Form - questions.....	91
13	Appendix: General Feedback Form – free text answers.....	97
14	Appendix: Homeless Data Portal - Frequently Asked Questions.....	100
15	Appendix: MOOC enrolments per residence country and open answers.....	103
15.1	MOOC enrolments per residence country of the participants for the 1st, 2nd and both editions	103
15.2	MOOC open answers.....	105
15.2.1	Which part of the MOOC did you like most and why?.....	105
15.2.2	Would you like to add any general remarks?	108
16	Appendix: Tutorial videos’ open answers.....	109
17	Appendix: Serious game’s open answers.....	110

1 Summary and highlights

The user statistics and feedback collected throughout the project provide valuable insights into the use of the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access (VA) Portal and its associated services. The VA Portal has served as the central entry point, with 297 registered users, 4,071 page views and 2,557 unique page views between March 2023 and August 2025. Peaks in activity coincided with major events such as ACTRIS Week, the ATMO-ACCESS annual meetings and the final meeting, showing the impact of targeted promotion. Feedback on the VA Portal was largely positive, with users satisfied with access and usability.

The Homeless Data Portal has proven its value for curating and hosting datasets not fully supported by existing infrastructures. In total 689 visits were registered, leading to 36 requests and 1,418 datasets, with 173 DOIs and 1,245 PIDs assigned, across six projects. While workflows for RI-type datasets were reported as smooth, more complex or non-standard data remain challenging. The introduction of a FAQ section improved usability.

The Time Series Analysis service grew steadily since June 2023, with 671 unique visits and 4,066 dataset API requests, averaging 170 requests per month. Usability improvements such as a detailed user guide, clearer station maps and better ergonomics were well received. Feedback emphasized the usefulness of the service while also requesting downloadable processed data and broader dataset availability.

The ACTRIS Footprint Analysis Service recorded 1,820 visits, 132 requests and 1,259 FLEXPART products created. Updates included better documentation, download scripts and mapping, while 12 publications already reference ATMO-ACCESS and the service. Feedback highlighted the need for training resources, with sustainability depending on long-term funding. The ICOS Footprint Service showed strong uptake with 1,685 footprint animations displayed, 1,137 model runs and 485 downloads. Seven publications reference the service, and feedback stressed the importance of traceability, citation guidance and continuity beyond the project. The IAGOS service received 656 unique visits and 11,514 footprints displayed, with enhancements such as daily updates, new emission data and improved ergonomics. Users emphasized its simplicity and usefulness.

Online training services, including the MOOC, tutorial videos and the serious game, were highly successful, in terms of number of participants and collection of valuable feedback. More than 1,300 participants were enrolled in the two editions of the MOOC, and the feedback from the 1st edition's learners were highly valuable to improve the course for the 2nd edition. Despite the limiting time between their release and the collection of feedback, the tutorial videos were watched several hundred times, and respondents to the surveys appreciated the format to

better understand instrumentation, or analysis tools, recommending deeper content and more case studies. The serious game was considered as a good entry point to the topic for young learners, with many possibilities to expand the game suggested by the respondents to the survey.

Overall, the services have delivered strong user engagement, broad scientific impact and high satisfaction across all areas, demonstrated by the large amount of service requests, curated datasets with DOIs, generated footprints and a growing number of scientific publications.

2 Introduction

This report gives a final overview of feedback from users and the statistics on use of the services offered through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access (VA) Portal for the period from launch until the 1st of August 2025. The [VA Portal](#) gives access to several online services: the [ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal](#), the [Time Series Analysis](#), three different [Trajectory and Footprint analysis tools](#), [Massive Open Online Course \(MOOC\)](#), several [training tutorials](#) and a [serious game](#). Each of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) in ATMO-ACCESS are responsible for different trajectory and footprint services depending on components and observation platforms, namely Greenhouse Gases (ICOS), Tropospheric vertical gradients (IAGOS) and Aerosol distribution and source analysis (ACTRIS).

Usage statistics in this report are based on defined service-specific metrics to ensure transparency and consistent interpretation across services. As different services apply different counting methods, a dedicated *Usage metrics* chapter provides formal definitions and explains how usage figures should be interpreted.

Feedback is given by user panels, internal feedback, e-mails, discussions at meetings and a general feedback form. User panels consist of a small group of selected central users and groups within the RIs that comment on the service in dedicated meetings. The general feedback form is a form available at <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access-feedback-form/>. The general feedback form was updated between D10.1 and D10.2, and each of these reports included only the latest feedback. However, since this is the last report, all answers to the feedback form are included, with a comment on the changes over time and new feedback for the latest period. The form has been visible in the VA portal for the duration of the project and sent out by email to all users that have agreed to share their e-mail addresses.

3 Usage metrics

This chapter defines the usage metrics applied throughout the report to ensure transparent and consistent interpretation across services.

Visits are recorded when a user enters a webpage or performs a tracked action; a new visit is counted after 30 minutes of inactivity. Visits and unique visits are tracked using IP addresses and therefore represent an approximation of user activity rather than exact individual counts. Shared institutional IP addresses may represent multiple users, while dynamic IP addresses may generate multiple counts for the same user. Consequently, there is not a one-to-one relationship between IP addresses and individual users, and the metric should primarily be interpreted as an indicator of trends in service usage over time. Requests represent service-specific user actions (e.g. data curation requests, model runs, or dataset access) and therefore differ between services. Where implemented and available, usage statistics also include download counts of accessible products such as model run outputs. As definitions and denominators vary between services, metrics are not directly comparable across services.

For the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) editions, users must register using their email address for each edition in which they participate. This allows the number of users to be counted directly based on registered participants. For the tutorial videos, usage is measured by the number of views of each video. Views are tracked either through the ATMO-ACCESS website for interactive videos or through the ATMO-ACCESS YouTube channel for videos without interactive elements. For the serious game, usage statistics are measured by the number of accesses to the dedicated webpage hosting the game.

These statistics follow the recommendations given in [D10.3 - Report on long-term strategy of VA activities and the new services in ATMO-ACCESS, taking into account the tools developed in WP5 and their best usage for science, management and outreach](#). Detailed definitions and counting rules are provided in the tables below.

Visits	A session recorded when a user enters a webpage or performs an action, reset after 30 minutes of inactivity.
Unique visits	Visits identified by unique IP addresses (IP-based counting; not a one-to-one representation of individual persons).
VA portal entries	Button clicks from the VA portal to individual services (entry count, not confirmed service usage).
Requests	A service-specific user action triggering processing or data retrieval (e.g., data curation requests, model runs,

	dataset access through APIs, or footprint displays), depending on the service.
Dataset accessed	Dataset selected in Step "Select datasets" via RI APIs in the Time Series Analysis service.
Dataset curated / DOI coined	A dataset fully processed by an RI and assigned a DOI or PID.
Model run	A specific type of request corresponding to the execution of a STILT or FLEXPART model calculation.
Download	Packaged model results downloaded by a user.
Footprint animation/view	A footprint displayed for a selected station and time period in a viewer interface.
Footprint day	One simulated day consisting of eight 3-hourly footprints.
MOOC participants	Number of registered users enrolled in a MOOC edition
MOOC completion	Number of participants obtaining a success badge after completing the final quiz
Video views	Number of views of a tutorial video on the website or YouTube.

Table 1: Overview and definitions of usage metrics used for reporting Virtual Access services.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
VA portal	Visits	Total page views of the VA portal	Includes repeated visits by same IP
	Unique visits	Unique page views based on IP addresses	IP-based; internal/external not distinguished
	VA portal entries	Button clicks to individual services	Counts entries, not confirmed use
Homeless Data Portal	Visits	Visits to the Homeless Data Portal webpage	IP-based
	Requests	Unique data curation issues submitted	Multiple datasets may belong to one request
	Dataset curated / DOI coined	Datasets processed and assigned DOI/PIDs	One request may include multiple datasets
Time Series Analysis	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to service	IP-based
	Dataset accessed	Datasets selected via RI APIs	1 request = 1 dataset access

ACTRIS Footprint analysis service	Visits	Visits to web interface	IP-based
	Requests	FLEXPART model run requests submitted via form	Tracked in Redmine. One request may generate multiple products.
ICOS Footprint analysis service	Footprint animation/view	Footprint animation displayed in the STILT results viewer	Counted per display event; each view may include up to one year of footprints
	Model run	STILT model runs started	1 run may cover multiple days
	Downloads	Model results downloaded	1 download may include multiple days
	Footprint day	Simulated footprint days generated	1 day = 8 footprints
IAGOS Footprint	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to viewer	IP-based
	Requests	Footprints displayed in viewer	Counted per display event
MOOC	MOOC Participants	Registered learners per course edition	Count based on FUN platform registrations
	MOOC Completion	Participants obtaining success badge	Passing grade $\geq 67\%$
Tutorial videos	Video views	Number of views per tutorial video	Includes ATMO-ACCESS website and YouTube views
Serious game	Visits	Visits to the webpage hosting the serious game	Page views used as visits.

Table 2: Overview of usage metrics applied per Virtual Access service, including counting rules and limitations.

4 Virtual Access Portal

The ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal provides access to all online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project.

ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal

This portal provides you with access to the new online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project. This include access to:

Homeless data portal:

A portal for submission of measurement data from research projects, not associated to any long-term projects/networks nor sustainable data centres.

Footprint analysis tool for greenhouse gases, aerosols, reactive trace gases:

Model tools for interpretation of measurement data both measured at the ground and from aircrafts. You can request model runs to produce data products (e.g footprint, source contributions) for your decided locations, or search and use the already produced products.

Time series analysis:

Identify, utilize and combine data more effectively across RIs and data repositories, including data coverage, collocation of data and visualisation of data.

Massive open online course (MOOC)

Online course 'Atmospheric Research Infrastructures: Sharing the future of our atmosphere'. – The 2nd edition will start on May 12, 2025 - Registrations from March 31, 2025

LOGIN

i You need to register to get access to the services. These services offered by ATMO-ACCESS are pilots for improvement over the project period. Accordingly, we need registration of users to get feedback and access statistic of the various services to meet the project requirements and increase the possibility of more funding for further development. When we collect personal data (e-mail) it is only for making it possible to contact you by e-mail. The information will be stored maximum 6 months after project completion, and you will only be contacted to provide feedback.

Figure 1: ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal (link: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/>)

When using the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, the user is required to log in, as seen in Figure 1. This is to gain statistics for the project, and to collect feedback on the services developed. Figure 2 shows the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal after login, with buttons giving access to “Data curation of homeless data”, “Trajectory and footprint analysis”, “Tools for analysing time series” and “Online training service”. The “Trajectory and footprint analysis” service includes one tool for each RI, which is Greenhouse Gases (ICOS), Tropospheric vertical gradients (IAGOS) and Aerosol distribution and source analysis (ACTRIS).

Lise Eder_Murberg

[GIVE FEEDBACK](#)

ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal

This portal provides you with access to the new online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project. This include access to:

- **Homeless data portal:**
A portal for submission of measurement data from research projects, not associated to any long-term projects/networks nor sustainable data centres.
- **Footprint analysis tool for greenhouse gases, aerosols, reactive trace gases:**
Model tools for interpretation of measurement data both measured at the ground and from aircrafts. You can request model runs to produce data products (e.g footprint, source contributions) for your decided locations, or search and use the already produced products.
- **Time series analysis:**
Identify, utilize and combine data more effectively across RIs and data repositories, including data coverage, collocation of data and visualisation of data.
- **Massive open online course (MOOC)**
Online course 'Atmospheric Research Infrastructures: Sharing the future of our atmosphere'. – **The 2nd edition will start on May 12, 2025 - Registrations from March 31, 2025**

Data curation of homeless data

Trajectory and footprint analysis

Tools for analysing time series

Online training service

Figure 2: ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal page after login, including a “give feedback” button that takes you to the general feedback form.

4.1 Updates throughout the project

The Virtual Access Portal has been updated with a QR code that links directly to the portal, making it easier for people to access when promoting it in presentations at meetings, posters, flyers etc. Furthermore, when logged into the portal, the VA Portal includes a “Give Feedback” button that directs users to the general feedback form.

4.2 Statistics on use of the online services

Statistics on the use of the ATMO-ACCESS online services are tracked in several ways.

- Visits to the ATMO-ACCESS VA entry website are tracked using Matomo¹. The number of visits/page views to the VA page (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/>) is provided in subsection 4.2.1.
- Access to the different services through the VA portal is tracked by counting hits on the corresponding access buttons.
- Each service independently tracks its effective usage by recording specific interactions and activities performed by users. This may include metrics such as the number of datasets accessed, model runs completed, or data curation requests processed. These detailed records provide a deeper understanding of how the services are utilized beyond mere access counts.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
VA portal	Visits	Total page views of the VA portal	Includes repeated visits by same IP
	Unique visits	Unique page views based on IP addresses	IP-based; internal/external not distinguished
	VA portal entries	Button clicks to individual services	Counts entries, not confirmed use

Table 3: Overview of usage metrics for VA portal, including counting rules and limitations.

4.2.1 User activity on the VA portal

The VA Portal's usage is monitored alongside visits to the main ATMO-ACCESS project webpage (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/>). Activity on the VA portal web page is thus measured by metrics such as 'page views' and 'unique page views' from the tracking system, with the latter determined by unique IP addresses. Furthermore, the users have to register with e-mail to the VA portal to access the services. One user in the VA portal can access several services.

Table 4 shows the number of registered users, overall page views and unique page views between 23rd March 2023 and 1st August 2025. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the monthly VA portal unique page views and page views, respectively. Peaks in March and May 2023 is due to the announcements of new services to the VA portal. The high period between October – December 2023 correlates with ACTRIS Week 2023, Svalbard Science Conference and IAGOS Users' meetings, all places where the VA services have been promoted. Lastly the high peak in March

¹ Matomo is an open-source web analytics tool (<https://matomo.org/>)

- May 2024 corresponds with ATMO-ACCESS Annual Meeting of 2024 and the ACTRIS Science Conference. High peak around March 2025 corresponds with the final user panels for the VA services developed in WP5 and the ATMO-ACCESS final meeting.

Registered users	297
Page views	4071
Unique page views	2557

Table 4: Overview of VA Portal page views and unique page views between 23rd March 2023 and 1st August 2025.

Figure 3: Monthly 'VA Portal' unique page views (until 1st of August 2025).

Figure 4: Monthly 'VA Portal' page views (until 1st of August 2025).

4.2.2 Service access via the VA portal

Access to the different services in the Virtual Access portal is tracked by counting hits on each of the entry buttons. Table 5 shows the entries to the different services for the period between 23rd March 2023 and 1st August 2025. Please note that these statistics are missing for the period between April 2025 and July 2025 due to a data collection issue that was detected late and fixed on July 29. This did not affect the previous statistics (registered users, page views and unique page views)

Footprints (all 3 services)	1090
Homeless data portal	280
Time series analysis	362
Online training service	27

Table 5: Entries to the different services between 23rd March 2023 and 1st August 2025. Statistics missing for the period between April 2025 – July 2025 due to a data collection issue.

4.3 Feedback from the general feedback form

The questions asked in the general feedback form for ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Services can be found here: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access-feedback-form/> and in Appendix 12.

Throughout the project there are two versions of the feedback form. The first form was available at the VA portal from 12th of September 2023. It was updated on the 7th of October 2024, with slightly different wording and two added questions. The form has been distributed by email to users that have logged into the VA portal. Despite several actions to promote the form has been taken, the form has only been filled in by 24 users in the project period.

The answers related to the Virtual Access Portal are compiled in this section, while the more specific answers applying to the different services are included in the chapters describing the feedback to these services.

Figure 5 shows where the users responding to the form first heard about the online services within the ATMO-ACCESS project, showing that information on the ATMO-ACCESS website, direct mailing from RIs, information received by colleagues/personal contacts and information received at events have been the most successful. Figure 6 shows that most answers in the form are to the Time Series Analysis tool, then the Homeless Data Portal and that all of the Footprint services have gotten the same number of answers. The MOOC got the least number of answers, but these services have also had a separate feedback form with a much larger number of answers. Figure 7 shows an evaluation of the access to the online services from the Virtual Access Portal, where most answers are between OK and Very satisfied.

How did you find out about the online services supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project?

24 answers

Figure 5: Answers to "How did you find out about the online services supported by the ATMO-ACCESS project?". 24 answers in total.

Service accessed

24 answers

Figure 6: Answers to "Service accessed". 24 answers in total. Users are encouraged to complete the form once for each service they want to give feedback on.

Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>

24 answers for first 2 questions, 21 answers for last

Figure 7: Answers to “Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>”. 24 answers in total for the two first statements, 21 answers for the last statement (First version of the feedback form only asked to people accessing the footprint services the last statement).

5 ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

The ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>) provides users with a portal for data curation of atmospheric measurement data. The portal is set up to serve scientists producing atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and TransNational Access (TNA) activities that have so far not been included into any data management and data curation system. These data sets are referred to as “homeless data” as they are not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centres. The goal of the portal is to make more atmospheric data (collected during campaigns and via TNA) available to the end-user, as well as to provide benefits for data custodians², by tracking the access and use of their data and getting access to RI specific tools for curation.

Making the data accessible through a FAIR³ data centre is the most efficient way to ensure long-term curation and promote visibility and access to data by a large user community. This

² The individual or organization that has accountability and responsibility for the data and ensures appropriate care and maintenance of the resource.

³ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>)

homeless data portal makes these data well documented for use and easily available for future use.

All requests for data curation and archiving services will be handled by the relevant research infrastructures (RI), seamless for the users. The architecture of the portal is described in section 2 of deliverable [D5.1 – Detailed requirements and \(non-\) technical specifications for all services based on the user consultations](#).

The starting page of the Homeless Data Portal is shown in Figure 8. The user gets information about the portal and available options: 1) To request data curation and archiving, 2) to access ATMO-ACCESS related data, and 3) to request general support. Both option 1) and 3) are request forms to be filled out by the user, and these requests are tracked in a redmine⁴ issue tracker by data curators. The general feedback form is included as a button on the starting page and the “FAQ and support” page.

⁴ <https://www.redmine.org/>

ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

The Homeless data portal is a portal for data curation of atmospheric measurement data. The portal is set up to serve scientists producing atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and TNA activities that are normally not included in any data management and data curation system and activity. These data sets are "homeless data", not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centers. The goal of the portal is to make more data available to the end-user, as well as providing benefits for data collectors in terms of usage tracking and access to RI (Research Infrastructure) specific tools for curation and data access.

All request for data curation and archiving services will be handled by a relevant research infrastructure. You will be contacted by e-mail after your request.

To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Feedback form](#)

<p>Data Archiving and Curation</p> <p>Apply for data curation and archiving services through the atmospheric RIs</p> <p>Access Services</p>	<p>Data Access</p> <p>Search ATMO-ACCESS related data from TNA and campaign activities</p> <p>Search Data</p>	<p>General Support</p> <p>Send a request if you have questions regarding the data in ATMO-ACCESS</p> <p>Get Support</p>
---	---	---

Figure 8: ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal Starting page (link: <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>).

5.1 Updates throughout the project

Throughout the project period, significant progress has been made in addressing the feedback provided, with several updates implemented to enhance user experience and functionality. A new comprehensive Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) section has been introduced, making it easier for users to find answers to common queries. This addition is located in the support section of the Homeless Data Portal, as shown in Figure 9.

Virtual Access Feedback

To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Feedback form](#)

FAQ

Frequently Asked Questions about the ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

What does "homeless data" refer to and who can use this service? ^
In the ATMO-ACCESS Project "homeless data" refers to data sets not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centers. This includes data sets from Transnational Access (TNA) activities, research campaigns and 'short-term' national or international research projects. Anyone with data which falls under the classification of "homeless data", as described above, can use the service.
Is the service free of charge? v
Will my data be associated with the term "homeless data"? v
Can I request curation for stations, instruments or methods not already in the RIs? v
What to expect from us after submitting a request? v
What is expected by me? v
Which research infrastructure (RI) should I expect to be contacted by? v
Are there any tools for formatting the data correctly? v
What benefits are there to using the Homeless Data Portal, compared to storing the data by myself? v
Will I get DOI(s) for my data set(s) and what is a collection DOI? v

Figure 9: FAQ and support page of The Homeless Data Portal.

Is this a collection of datasets?
<input type="text" value="Yes"/> v
If it is a collection of datasets, do you wish us to provide a collection DOI?
<input type="text" value="No"/> v

Figure 10: Newly added questions to the data curation request form, where the user can specify if the request is a collection of datasets and if the user wish to have a collection DOI on the datasets.

Users now have the option to request collection DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) for submitted collections of datasets, as illustrated in Figure 10. To further streamline the collection of user insights, a feedback form has been prominently integrated on both the start page and the FAQ and support page, as seen in Figure 8 and Figure 9. Additionally, the portal has been actively promoted to the scientific community, with details provided in *D10.4 - Report on the suitability of the different services modalities taking into account finances, outreach and scientific impact*.

5.2 Statistics on use of the Homeless Data Portal

Statistics on the use of the Homeless Data Portal are tracked in several ways. Firstly, as number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then the number of visits to the Homeless Data Portal itself (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>), and lastly as the number of requests made through the portal. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (entry through the Homeless Data Portal button, as described in subsection 4.2.2) and visits to the web-page itself gives an indication of the number of people entering directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. Requests in the Homeless Data Portal are logged in the issue tracker when a user submits a curation request for a data set or a collection of datasets through <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no/request>.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
Homeless Data Portal	Visits	Visits to the Homeless Data Portal webpage	IP-based
	Requests	Unique data curation issues submitted	Multiple datasets may belong to one request
	Dataset curated / DOI coined	Datasets processed and assigned DOI/PIDs	One request may include multiple datasets

Table 6: Overview of usage metrics for Homeless Data Portal, including counting rules and limitations.

5.2.1 Users' activity on the Homeless Data Portal

Use of the Homeless Data Portal is tracked using Matomo. In Figure 11, a map shows the distribution of the use of to the portal worldwide (689 visits) and in Europe (554 visits). The access numbers are higher than the metrics from the VA portal where the Homeless Data Portal button had 280 entries, showing that some users access the Homeless Data Portal directly and some users access through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal. Table 7 lists the countries using the Homeless Data Portal most, and the number of visits for each country. Several developers and curators working on the Homeless Data Portal are located in Norway and France, hence higher numbers for these countries are expected since Matomo only counts by IP addresses and does

not differentiate between internal ATMO-ACCESS users and external users. The United States shows high visit numbers to the Homeless Data Portal, which may reflect the current challenges in climate data availability and management in the U.S.; this also highlights the future potential of the portal as a tool to strengthen data security and collaboration between the U.S. and Europe. Lastly, Figure 12 shows the number of visits and actions per visit over time. Actions comprise, for instance, page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches.

Figure 11: User map showing on the left-hand side a total of 689 visits to the Homeless Data Portal worldwide and on the right-hand side 554 visits in Europe from 23.03.2023 - 01.08.2025.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Norway	113
United States	101
France	67
Italy	49
Sweden	49
Netherlands	37
Germany	36
Greece	28
Spain	27
Finland	25

Table 7: Countries with the most visits to the Homeless Data Portal from 23.03.2023 - 01.08.2025.

Visits Over Time

Visits Over Time

Figure 12: Two graphs showing visits and actions per visit over time from 23.03.2023 - 01.08.2025. The upper graph shows both number of visits (in blue) and actions per visit (in orange), while the lower graph shows only actions per visit to properly see the scale. This gives an average of 2.2 actions (page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit.

5.2.2 Data requests through the Homeless Data Portal

Requests in the Homeless Data Portal are compiled in a redmine issue tracker after a user requests the curation service through <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no/request>. After a request shows up in the issue tracker, the data curators assign which RI the data set(s) are associated to, and the data set(s) follow the normal data curation workflow. Statistics on the user requests for the service can be found in Table 8. The table counts the total number of user requests, the number of unique requests (some have sent similar requests two or more times for the same set of data), and open and closed issues. Open issues may arise because the issue was recently received or because only part of a collection of datasets has been sent to the RI and curated, while additional datasets are still pending. The 'Number of datasets curated' refers to the number of datasets that have been fully curated by one of the RIs and assigned a PID (Persistent IDentifier). The result of 1,418 datasets with 173 DOIs and 1245 PIDs assigned is a great result for the project, which highlights the importance of the Homeless Data Portal and the efforts put in by both data curators at the RIs and data submitters. Lastly, the Table 8 lists the project associations that have requested curation services and the RIs their request have been associated with.

Over the summer 2025 about 10 requests came through the Homeless Data Portal, where 5 requests were from the CleanCloud project on different types of ACTRIS data. ACTRIS has decided to take on the CleanCloud requests as a strategic decision and will continue with these even after the project. ATMO-ACCESS will get recognition for these datasets as part of the work

have been carried out in the project. The remaining requests will get a standardized description of the RI workflow, but with a significant reduction in training/support from the RIs.

Number of requests (unique)	36 (30)
Open issues in progress	12
Closed issues (unique)	24 (18)
Number of datasets curated (and given PIDs)	1,418 datasets (173 DOIs for long time series or collections and 1245 PIDs for daily data)
Project associations	6 (ATMO-ACCESS TNA, RI-URBANS, WeBASOOP, ICOS, EMPIRE, CleanCloud, ITINERIS)
Number of requests associated to ACTRIS DC	32
Number of requests associated to IAGOS DC	0
Number of requests associated to ICOS carbon portal	4

Table 8: Statistics on requests through the Homeless Data Portal from launch to 01.08.2025.

Looking ahead, the intention is to keep the Homeless Data Portal open for all RIs, but with the end of the project funding, the resources available for training and support will be significantly reduced. This limitation will require each RI to carefully consider which requests they can take on, and it may ultimately restrict how broadly the service can be used.

5.3 Feedback from users on the Homeless Data Portal

Feedback on the service is provided through user panel meetings and e-mail.

5.3.1 User panel for Homeless Data Portal

User panels consist of meetings with a small group of selected users, and within the RIs that comment on the service. The user panel meetings are described in [D10.1](#), [D10.2](#) and [M22](#).

The feedback on the Homeless Data Portal highlights its strong potential as a valuable service for curating and hosting datasets not fully supported by existing RIs. A general perception of the Homeless Data Portal was that for data similar to data already in the databases, the workflow was very smooth, while for more non-traditional datasets (lev3, model etc) it's not possible to use it.

5.3.2 Feedback form for the Homeless Data Portal

Figures 13 through 17 provide an overview of user feedback and evaluations related to the Homeless Data Portal. In Figure 13, the user rated the functionality and relevance of the service, with responses ranging from "OK" to "Very satisfied". Figure 14 reflects the user's willingness to recommend the service to a colleague, with all users answering that they are likely to

recommend it. In Figure 15, the user indicated a preference for training formats such as videos and e-learning. Figure 16 highlights the user's general positive evaluation of the Homeless Data Portal, and Figure 17 outlines the perceived benefits, such as time savings and easy data access.

Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used

4 answers

Figure 13: : Answers to the question "Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used".

Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?

4 answers

Figure 14: Answers to the question "Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?".

Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

4 answers

Figure 15: Answers to the question "Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?".

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

4 answers

Figure 16: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective".

Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

4 answers

Figure 17: Answers to the question "Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt".

6 Time Series Analysis

The Time Series Analysis service provides users a tool to identify, use and combine data across RIs and data repositories. It aims at serving a large variety of users (students, academics, private or public organizations, NGOs, communities of projects, etc.) by providing a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for facilitating their exploration of multiple in situ datasets with long time series of different variables. The service makes accessible the most commonly used basic metrics (e.g. means, percentiles) and statistical analysis (e.g. trends), as well as visualization tools to look at e.g. 2D or 3D scatter plots. The combination of different variables important for climate and air quality recorded by ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS allows users to explore relevant cross-cutting issues. An example of the search functionality for available variables of the Time Series Analysis service is shown in Figure 18.

The architecture of the service is described in section 4 of deliverable [D5.1 – Detailed requirements and \(non-\) technical specifications for all services based on the user consultations](#).

Time-series analysis

GIVE FEEDBACK

0. Information 1. Search datasets 2. Select datasets 3. Filter data 4. Data analysis

NEXT

Select variables

Select all / none

- ACP - Aerosol Chemical Properties
- AP - Pressure (surface)
- APP - Aerosol Physical Properties
- AT - Temperature (near surface)
- CH4 - Methane
- CIP - Cloud Properties
- CO - Carbon Monoxide
- CO2 - Carbon Dioxide
- N2O - Nitrous Oxide
- NO2 - NO2
- O3 - Ozone
- RH - Water Vapour (surface)
- WSD - Surface Wind Speed and direction

Select stations

Stations map

Map background: open street map carto positron

Selected stations (you can refine your selection here)

- REV (Revin, ACTRIS)
- BRU (Brussels, IAGOS)
- DUS (Dusseldorf, IAGOS)
- FRA (Frankfurt, IAGOS)
- HEI (Heidelberg, ICOS)
- JUE (Jülich, ICOS)
- KIT (Karlsruhe, ICOS)

Figure 18: ATMO-ACCESS Time Series Analysis Search datasets page (link: <https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-timeseries>).

6.1 Updates throughout the project

For the entire duration of the project, numerous suggestions expressed in the user feedback were implemented and resulted in the service improvement:

- A detailed user guide is available. It makes a complete tour of the service's functionalities and features.
- A presentation of the map with RI's stations was greatly improved (co-located stations issue resolved, better map readability).
- Overall ergonomics and clarity of the user interface of the service was improved.
- The datasets available have been improved with new variables and new datasets have been added.

6.2 Statistics on use of the Time Series Analysis service

Statistics on the use of the Time Series Analysis are tracked in several ways. Firstly, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then via the number of visits to the Time-series analysis web-service itself, and lastly via the number of requests through the service. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (clicks on the “Tools for analysing time series” button, as described in subsection 4.2.2) and visits to the web-page itself gives an indication of the number of people going directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. Each RI provides access to their datasets through a dedicated API that is requested by the service. The number of requests to the service is considered similar to the number of datasets accessed through the RIs data access APIs⁵. This means the number of datasets accessed in step “2. Select datasets” in the service, which is the step after “1. Search datasets” which is shown in Figure 18. The statistics are available from June 2023 until August 1st, 2025.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
Time Series Analysis	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to service	IP-based
	Dataset accessed	Datasets selected via RI APIs	1 request = 1 dataset access

Table 9: Overview of usage metrics for Time Series Analysis, including counting rules and limitations.

6.2.1 Usage metrics for the Time Series Analysis service

User visits to the Time Series Analysis give an indication about how many people are using the service. Figure 14 shows the number of unique visits over time. The total number of unique visits is 671 for the period from June 22, 2023, to August 1st, 2025, where the high peak at around 26th of September most likely is when the first user panel was held. Unique visits refer to visits made by unique IP addresses. The average number of visits is around 28 visits a month since the service has been released.

⁵ An application programming interface (API) is a way for two or more computer programs to communicate with each other. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software.

Time series service - Visits

Figure 19: Number of unique visits over time – Time series service from June 22, 2023 to August 1, 2025.

6.2.2 Data analysis requests in the Time Series Analysis Service

The number of requests is the number of datasets accessed through the RIs data access APIs. This means the number of datasets accessed in step “2. Select datasets” in the service. Figure 20 shows the number of API requests over time. The total number of requests for the time series service is 4,066 for the period June 22, 2023, to August 1, 2025. On average, 84 datasets were requested by each user. The average number of requests is around 170 requests a month since the service has been released.

Time series service - Requests

Figure 20: Number of requests over time – Time series service from June 22, 2023 to August 1, 2025.

6.3 Feedback from users on the Time Series Analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided in two ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Through the general feedback form

This compiles the feedback given from the entire project.

6.3.1 User panel for Time Series Analysis service

The first Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the time-series analysis service took place in September 2023 and a second one in April 2024 and the last one in March 2025. General feedback about the main features of the service (filtering and analysis) was very positive. Remarks from the last panel concerned the ergonomics of the service that has been updated in accordance. The main feedback was to propose the possibility to download the data generated to plot the figures. This feature will be implemented but after the end of the project.

More details on the feedback are available in Milestones 20, 20 and 22 (Feedback meetings with user panel, discussion of updates, <https://www.atmo-access.eu/deliverables-and-milestones/>).

6.3.2 Feedback form for the Time Series Analysis service

Figures 16 through 20 provide an overview of user feedback and evaluations related to the Time Series Analysis Service. In Figure 21, the user rated the functionality and relevance of the service, with responses ranging from “Poor” to “Very satisfied”. Figure 22 reflects the user's willingness to recommend the service to a colleague, with most users answering that they are likely to recommend it while two users would most likely not. In Figure 23, the user indicated an equal preference for various training formats, including videos, e-learning, and a library of resources, demonstrating an interest in support materials. Figure 24 highlights the user’s general positive evaluation of the Time Series Analysis, and Figure 25 outlines the perceived benefits, such as time savings and immediate access to results.

Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used

10 answers

Figure 21: Answers to the question "Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used".

Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?

7 answers

Figure 22: Answers to the question "Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?".

Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

6 answers

Figure 23: Answers to the question "Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?".

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

10 answers

Figure 24: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective".

Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

9 answers

Figure 25: Answers to the question "Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt".

7 ACTRIS footprint analysis service for aerosol and trace gas measurements

The ACTRIS footprint analysis service provides model tools to users for the interpretation of ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations. The users can request model runs to produce data products (e.g., footprints, source contributions) for defined ground-based stations and products or search and use data products for existing locations. Footprint products are used to provide air mass origin information that helps understand the trajectory of the air masses and to analyze atmospheric observations. Source contribution products give modelled contributions to a variable from a given sector e.g., modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from residential and commercial sector. All products are generated using the FLEXPART (FLEXible PARTicle dispersion model) and include footprint analysis for air masses arriving at the station on a 3-hour time resolution for 20 days back in time, except for near-real-time (NRT) products which are for the last 3 days and include a 1-day forecast. Currently data products can be requested for the variables and categories described in Table 10.

Black carbon	Standard products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements at sites with long time series
Dust	Products for analysing dust events at various sites
Specialized black carbon	Tailored products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements from specific campaigns
Other	Tailored products for analysing land-use change, sulphate, CO and OC from specific campaigns
Microplastic	Tailored products for analysing microplastic (MP) measurements from specific campaigns
Near-Real-Time (NRT)	Footprint products to be used for analysing NRT data and 1 day forecast

Table 10: Current FLEXPART products available for ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations.

The starting page of the ACTRIS Footprint analysis service is shown in Figure 26. A user of this service has different options:

- i) to request new model runs,
- ii) to access current products already produced within ATMO-ACCESS, and
- iii) to get general support, e.g., for in-depth interpretation.

“Available FLEXPART Footprint products” shows ACTRIS stations with already processed standard black carbon footprint and source contribution products for years between 2007-2022 (within ATMO-ACCESS). The “FLEXPART Station map” shows a map of all stations with available products, where the marker for each station is dependent on the categories in Table 10.

ATMO-ACCESS

FLEXPART products for ground based aerosol and trace gas observations

FLEXPART Model Run

Request access to FLEXPART model run

[Request Access](#)

FLEXPART Products and Information

Access FLEXPART products and descriptions

[Access Data](#)

General Support

Do you have questions regarding the FLEXPART products in ATMO-ACCESS?

[Get Support](#)

To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Feedback form](#)

Overview of stations with FLEXPART products

Black carbon: Standard products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements at sites with long time series

Dust: Products for analysing dust events at various sites

Specialized black carbon: Tailored products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements from specific campaigns

Other: Tailored products for analysing landuse change, sulfate, CO and OC from specific campaigns

Microplastic: Tailored products for analysing microplastic (MP) measurements from specific campaigns

Near Real Time (NRT): Footprint products to be used for analysing NRT data and 1 day forecast

Figure 26: Starting page for ATMO-ACCESS Footprint products for ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations (link: <https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/>).

7.1 Updates throughout the project

Throughout the project, the ACTRIS footprint analysis service has undergone several updates aimed at improving functionality and addressing user feedback. The website now provides comprehensive documentation of its products, including detailed descriptions and selection parameters, available on the *FLEXPART products* page (see Figure 27 for Black Carbon).

To facilitate easier data access, download scripts have been introduced, enabling users to transfer complete datasets more efficiently. The mapping feature has also been upgraded to give a clearer overview of available products, making it simpler to identify and access relevant datasets. Importantly, the map now displays location names instead of the previous EBAS ID codes, further improving usability. In addition, several new locations have been added in response to user requests submitted through the portal.

Technical updates include the transition to ECMWF meteorological fields and ongoing migration to FLEXPART version 11. Forecast capabilities have been made available during the project, expanding the service's utility. Finally, citation requirements are now stated more clearly and are directly visible on the service page, ensuring users can reference the products correctly.

Black Carbon Organic Carbon Dust Microplastic NRT Sulfate and Landuse

Info on FLEXPART products for the webpage

- Upper left box selects **station code** that the user wants to view.
- Next two boxes on the right select **year** and **month** (2012-present).
- Then, the users select the product that he wants to view (Source Spec, Footprint, DOM BC, ENE BC, IND BC, FLR BC, SHP BC, WST BC, TRA BC, Fire BC, Total BC, Continental Spec, Age Spec).
- Final box on the right selects the **projection** (regional, global, polar).
- Buttons **FIRST**, **-10**, **PREV**, **NEXT**, **+10**, **LAST** navigate between different samples. For example, suppose we visualize product **Footprint** for station **ES0018G** for year **2020** and month **January** on 07-Jan-2020 at 18:00 to 21:00 (instance 55/248). The users navigate to the first footprint (01-Jan-2020 at 00:00 to 03:00) using the button **FIRST**, to the last footprint (31-Jan-2020 at 21:00 to 01-Feb-2020 at 00:00) with button **LAST**, to previous (07-Jan-2020 at 15:00 to 18:00) and next footprints (07-Jan-2020 at 21:00 to 08-Jan-2020 at 00:00) with buttons **PREV** and **NEXT**. With buttons **-10** and **+10**, the users can go ten timesteps backward (06-Jan-2020 at 12:00 to 15:00) or forward (09-Jan-2020 at 00:00 to 03:00) from the current timestep.
- Buttons **VIEW PLOT** and **NETCDF** (for map products) or **VIEW DATA** (for spectrum products) switch between plot visualization and links for download the data. Map products (Footprint, DOM BC, ENE BC, IND BC, FLR BC, SHP BC, WST BC, TRA BC, Fire BC, Total BC) are in gridded arrays and are given in netCDF format, while spectrum products (Source Spec, Continental Spec, Age Spec) are given in ascii format.

Explanation of products included in the webpage.

- **Footprint:** Footprint emissions sensitivity showing the probability of any release occurring in any grid-cell to reach the receptor (station) for 30 days particle tracking. **In newer versions of the product, the average column trajectory of the footprint is plotted on each map as a function of the height of the plume center (gray colorbar on the right). Each colored circle represents each day backward in time from the release. In addition, there is a timeseries plot under the map showing the plume height versus time backward in time (black line) and on the right secondary axes, the percentage of particles in the planetary boundary layer (PBL) in magenta color and the percentage of particles in the stratosphere (STRA) in blue. Each circle represents days backward from the release date and time.**
- **DOM BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from residential and commercial sector plotted on a map (three projections). DOM includes emissions from combustion in heating and cooking stoves and boilers in households and public and commercial buildings (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **ENE BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from energy production sector plotted on a map (three projections). ENE includes emissions from combustion processes in power plants and generators (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **IND BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from industrial combustion plotted on a map (three projections). IND includes emissions from industrial boilers and industrial production processes (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **FLR BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from gas flaring plotted on a map (three projections). FLR includes emissions from oil and gas facilities (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **SHP BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from shipping activities in in-land waters plotted on a map (three projections) (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **WST BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from waste treatment and disposal sector plotted on a map (three projections). WST resembles emissions from waste incineration and treatment (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **TRA BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from transportation sector plotted on a map (three projections). TRA includes emissions from all land-based transport of goods, animals and persons on road networks and off-road activities (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **Fire BC:** Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from open biomass burning (excluding agricultural fires) plotted on a map (three projections) (GFEDv4, Giglio et al., <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrg.20042>).
- **Total BC:** The sum of the BC contributions.
- **Source Spec:** Timeseries plot of modelled concentrations in 3h resolution showing the contribution of each source (DOM BC, ENE BC, IND BC, FLR BC, SHP BC, WST BC, TRA BC, Fire BC) to surface BC.
- **Continent Spec:** Timeseries plot of modelled concentrations in 3h resolution showing the continental contribution (OCE: Ocean, GNL: Greenland, SA: South America, CA: Central America, NA: North America, AFR: Africa, EUR: Europe, RUS: Russia, ASI: Asia excluding Russian part, AUS: Australia) to surface BC.
- **Age Spec:** Timeseries plot of modelled concentrations in 3h resolution showing the age contribution of the plume to surface BC. The latter shows how "fresh" or "old" the air arriving at the receptor is.

Figure 27: Comprehensive documentation of the products, providing detailed descriptions of available products and parameters for selection on the "FLEXPART products" page for Black Carbon.

7.2 Statistics on use of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the footprint analysis service are tracked in several ways. First it is the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal, then the number of visits to the ACTRIS footprint analysis service itself (<https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/>) and lastly the

number of FLEXPART requests, i.e. the request forms filled out with request for model runs at a given station/location.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
ACTRIS Footprint analysis service	Visits	Visits to web interface	IP-based
	Requests	FLEXPART model run requests via form	Tracked in Redmine

Table 11: Overview of usage metrics for ACTRIS Footprint analysis service, including counting rules and limitations.

7.2.1 Usage metrics for the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Use of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page is tracked using Matomo. The user map in Figure 28 shows the distribution of entries worldwide (1820 visits) and in Europe (1438 visits). Table 12 lists the countries with the most users of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page, and the number of visits made by each country. Lastly, Figure 29 shows the visits and actions (e.g., page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit over time.

Figure 28: User map showing on the left-hand side a total of 1820 visits to the ACTRIS Footprint Analysis Service web-page worldwide, and on the right-hand side 1438 visits in Europe during 15.05.2023 - 01.08.2025.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Norway	442
United States	219
France	148
Italy	143
Switzerland	133
United Kingdom	75
Germany	72
Austria	66
Greece	66
Spain	61

Table 12: Countries with the most users of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page during 15.05.2023 - 01.08.2025.

Figure 29: Two graphs showing visits and actions per visit over time from 15.05.2023 - 01.08.2025. The upper graph shows both number of visits (in blue) and actions per visit (in orange), while the lower graph shows only actions per visit to properly see the scale. This gives an average of 2.1 actions (page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit.

7.2.2 Model requests in the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

The number of requests for the footprint analysis service is tracked in the Aeris Redmine issue tracker and is 132 requests between 15.05.2023-01.08.2025. Figure 30 shows which countries the different requests originate from, while Figure 31 shows the different type of products the requests have asked for. The ACTRIS footprint service started out with black carbon (BC) products, and has extended with other products such as dust, microplastics, NRT and more (other products) since the launch of the service, which corresponds with Figure 31 where BC is

the most demanded product type. As this service is new within this project, many ACTRIS sites have asked for the standardized products such as BC which can explain the high demand. The 132 requests correspond to 1,259 FLEXPART model products created, as a single request may generate several products depending on the number of stations, variables, or time periods requested. The evolution of requests and products provided can be seen in Figure 32.

Requests; Country overview

Figure 30: Diagram of FLEXPART requests in the period 15.05.23-01.08.25 divided by country.

Requests; Product type

Figure 31: Type of FLEXPART products that have been requested in the period 15.05.23-01.08.25.

FLEXPART footprints; Requests and products

Figure 32: Overview of FLEXPART requests and corresponding products created in the period 15.05.23-01.08.25. Axes for requests are on the left side, and axes for products are on the right side.

7.2.3 Scientific papers

Publications using the ACTRIS FLEXPART footprint analysis service in the ATMO-ACCESS project:

1. Popovicheva, O. B., Evangeliou, N., Kobelev, V. O., Chichaeva, M. A., Eleftheriadis, K., Gregorič, A., and Kasimov, N. S.: Siberian Arctic black carbon: gas flaring and wildfire impact, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 22, 5983–6000, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-5983-2022>, 2022. (OA)
2. Goßmann, I., Herzke, D., Held, A., Schulz, J., Nikiforov, V., Georgi, C., Evangeliou, N., Eckhardt, S., Gerdt, G., Wurl, O., and Scholz-Böttcher, B. M., Occurrence and backtracking of microplastic mass loads including tire wear particles in northern Atlantic air. *Nat Commun* 14, 3707 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39340-5> (OA)
3. Aves, A., Ruffell, H., Evangeliou, N., Gaw, S., and Revell, L. E.: Modelled sources of airborne microplastics collected at a remote Southern Hemisphere site, *Atmos. Environ.*, 325,120437, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2024.120437> , 2024. (OA)

4. Gidarakou, M., Papayannis, A., Kokkalis, P., Evangeliou, N., Vratolis, S., Remoundaki, E., Groot Zwaaftink, C., Eckhardt, S., Veselovskii, I., Mylonaki, M., Argyrouli, A., Eleftheriadis, K., Solomos, S., & Gini, M. I.: Optical and microphysical properties of the aerosols during a rare event of biomass-burning mixed with polluted dust, *Atmosphere*, 15, 190, <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos15020190>, 2024. (OA)
5. Hartz, W.F., Björnsdotter, M.K., Yeung, L.W.Y., Humby, J.D., Eckhardt, S., Evangeliou, N., Jogsten, .E., Kärrman, A., & Kallenborn, R.: Sources and Seasonal Variations of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) in Surface Snow in the Arctic, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.4c08854>, 2024. (OA)
6. Fang, W., Evangeliou, N., Eckhardt, S. Xiao, H., & Li, H. (2025) "Unprecedented shifts in aerosol pollution sources in China under a decade of clean air actions", *Nat.Communications Earth & Environment*, 6, 512, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-025-02487-8>.
7. Dada, L., Brem, B. T., Amarandi-Netedu, L.-M., Collaud Coen, M., Evangeliou, N., Hueglin, C., Nowak, N., Modini, R., Steinbacher, M., & Gysel-Beer, M. (2025) "Sources of ultrafine particles at a rural midland site in Switzerland", *Aerosol Research*, 3, 315-336, <https://doi.org/10.5194/ar-3-315-2025>.
8. Abbasi, S., Hashemi, N., Sabaliauskaite, V., Evangeliou, N., Dzingelevecius, N., Balciunas, A., & Dzingeleveciene, R. (2025) "Fluxes, residence times, and the budget of microplastics in the Curonian Lagoon", *Environmental Pollution*, 375, 126289, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2025.126289>.
9. Ballo, E.G., D'Andrea, W.J., Hoeg, H.I., Loftsgarden, K., Bajard, M., Eckhardt, S., Cassiani, M., Evangeliou, N., Bakke, J., & Krugger, K. (2025) "2000 years of climate, environmental, and societal variability in southeastern Norway from the annually laminated sediments of Lake Sagtjernet", *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 354, 109232, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2025.109232>.
10. Tichy, O., Evangeliou, N., Selivanova, A., & Smidl, V. (2025) "Inverse modeling of ¹³⁷Cs during Chernobyl 2020 wildfires without the first guess", *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, 16 (4), 102419, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apr.2025.102419>.
11. Brozova, A., Smidl, V., Tichy, O., & Evangeliou, N. (2025) "Spatial-temporal source term estimation using deep neural network prior and its application to Chernobyl wildfires", *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 488, 137510, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.137510>.
12. Jurkschat, L., Gill, A.J., Milner, R., Holzinger, R., Evangeliou, N., Eckhardt, S. & Materic, D. (2025) "Using a citizen science approach to assess nanoplastics pollution in remote high-altitude glaciers", *Nature Scientific Reports*, 15, 1864, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-84210-9>.

7.3 Feedback from users on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided in several ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Internal feedback
- Through the general feedback form

This compiles the feedback given from the entire project.

7.3.1 User panel on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

The User Panel met three times (September 2023, April 2024, and March 2025) and was generally impressed by the large number of available footprints and data products. Feedback focused on the need for clearer documentation, better station labelling, and a simple training video. Users also requested easier data access options, including viewing data without downloads, batch downloads, and an API for automated use. It was further recommended to provide clear guidance on acknowledging the project and to assign PIDs to downloadable results. While there is strong interest in continuing the service beyond ATMO-ACCESS, securing sustainable funding is essential, and promotion should continue through conferences, workshops, and scientific use cases. More detailed feedback is available in Milestones 20, 21 and 22 (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/deliverables-and-milestones/>)

7.3.2 Response on feedback form related to ACTRIS footprint analysis.

Figures 33 through 37 provide an overview of user feedback and evaluations related to the ACTRIS footprint analysis in the general feedback form. In Figure 33, the user rated the functionality and relevance of the service, with responses indicating "Poor" to "Very satisfied" ratings across various aspects. Figure 34 reflects the user's willingness to recommend the service to a colleague, with high ratings provided. In Figure 35, the users indicated a preference for various training formats, with both users wishing for videos, e-learning, interactive webinars and written documentation. Figure 36 highlights the users' positive evaluation of the FLEXPART footprints, and Figure 37 outlines the perceived benefits, such as scientific and technical support and immediate access to results.

Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used

4 answers

Figure 33: Answers to the question "Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used".

Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?

3 answers

Figure 34: Answers to the question "Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?".

Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

3 answers

Figure 35: Answers to the question "Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?".

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

4 answers

Figure 36: Answers to the question "Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective".

Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

4 answers

Figure 37: Answers to the question "Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt".

8 ICOS Footprint analysis service for greenhouse gases

The ICOS STILT station footprint calculation and viewing service allows users to explore greenhouse gas concentrations and footprints for ground-based stations in Europe.

The STILT results viewer (Figure 38) allows to select all footprint data available in the repository and to display an animation of the footprints together with the modelled CO₂ or CH₄ concentrations and contributions from different source categories. For ICOS stations and some selected other European stations, also the measured concentrations are included for comparison. The viewer also provides the option to download the model results.

The STILT calculation service allows users to interactively start new STILT model runs for any new location within the model domain (Figure 39).

The FLEXPART footprint service for passive tracers, implemented at ICOS, allows user to request the calculation of footprints for one or more stations through a web form accessible via the ATMO-ACCESS VA portal. These requests are handled manually and results are packaged according to the user preferences.

STILT results viewer

Download results Re-package results STILT worker Help

To keep our services free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback scheme to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

Give us Feedback

Legal mentions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004.
©Copyright: ATMO-ACCESS - 2021 - SEDOS (Service de Données OMP)

Figure 38: ATMO-ACCESS ICOS STILT results viewer page ([link: https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/viewer/](https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/viewer/)).

STILT calculation service Job starter

STILT viewer Help

Existing STILT stations

Select station here or on the map

Start new STILT run

Site id (letter code + altitude) [Load data](#)

Site name

ICOS station id

Country code — Select —

Latitude (decimal degree)

Longitude (decimal degree)

Altitude above ground (meters)

Start date (YYYY-MM-DD)

End date (YYYY-MM-DD)

[Submit STILT job](#)

Submitted STILT jobs

[Show details](#)

Job queue

- Site 'ERS040' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'FKL015' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'AR110' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'KAS' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'KAT100' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)

Running computations

- Site 'CRP014' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)

Finished computations

- Site 'BIS047' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'MHD' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'CRA060' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'BSO248' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'BRM212' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'BIK300' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'HPI' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'HPI' (2023-01-01 - 2023-01-01)

To keep our services free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Give us Feedback](#)

Legal mentions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004.
©Copyright ATMO-ACCESS - 2021 - SEDOO (Service de Données OMP)

Figure 39: ATMO-ACCESS ICOS STILT calculation service page (link: <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/worker/>).

8.1 Updates throughout the project

During the course of the project, the STILT footprint service was continuously improved and several features were implemented based on user feedback:

- The capability to calculate CH₄ concentrations was introduced. Subsequently, all existing concentration results were updated in the repository with CH₄ concentrations. Since then, both CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations have been calculated simultaneously in every STILT run.

- STILT model versions were regularly updated to align with developments in the central STILT repository.
- The STILT calculation service was deployed across multiple servers within the ICOS Carbon Portal, increasing computational throughput by distributing workloads across the servers.
- The STILT results viewer was extended to include CO₂ and CH₄ observations from additional stations in Europe that are not part of ICOS but contributed data to the European ObsPack compiled by ICOS. These additional datasets are now available for comparison with model results.
- A pre-selection option was added in the STILT results viewer, allowing users to filter stations by ICOS stations, other existing European stations, or all locations with model available model results. This feature streamlines the search and selection process via both the map and the drop-down list.
- The calculation service now requires users to provide not only a station ID but also a descriptive station name and the country in which the station is located. This additional metadata improves the reusability of results for other users.
- Navigation between the STILT results viewer page and the calculation service was improved, enabling users to move seamlessly between the two interfaces.
- User email addresses displayed in the calculation queue are now partially obscured, showing only the first and last three characters, thereby improving privacy.
- The documentation describing the provenance of model and input data was regularly updated and is included in every model result packaged for download.
- The user guide for STILT results viewer and calculation service was improved and is linked on every page.
- All documentation is available on the ICOS website without the need for ATMO-ACCESS login, increasing accessibility for the broader community.

In a later part of the project, a second footprint service for passive tracers, based on the FLEXPART model, was implemented at ICOS. In this service, the calculation of station footprints is requested via a separate web form added to the ATMO-ACCESS VA portal.

8.2 Statistics on use of the ICOS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the ICOS STILT station footprint calculation and viewing service are tracked through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal, recording the number of model runs started and result packages downloaded. The number of times the footprint animation was viewed on the ICOS STILT results viewer page is recorded only since 22 March 2024. The statistics are available since June 2023 until 1 August 2025

There was a gap in all statistics recorded in the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal between 23 April 2025 and 29 July 2025. The number of footprint animations displayed in the ICOS Footprint Viewer and number of model runs started in the ICOS Footprint Service were extracted from the statistics kept in the ICOS CP system for this period.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
ICOS Footprint analysis service	Footprint animation/view	Footprint animation displayed in the STILT results viewer	Counter per display event; each view includes up to one year of footprints
	Model run	STILT model runs started	1 run may cover multiple days
	Downloads	Model results downloaded	1 download may include multiple days
	Footprint day	Simulated footprint days generated	1 day = 8 footprints

Table 13: Overview of usage metrics for ICOS Footprint analysis service, including counting rules and limitations.

8.2.1 Usage Metrics for the ICOS Footprint Viewer

Figure 40 shows the number of times footprint animations were displayed on the ICOS STILT results viewer page. Each time a user selects a station and a year, all footprints and concentrations available for this time period are shown. The views are tracked separately since 22 March 2024.

Figure 40: Number of STILT footprint animations displayed in the ICOS footprint service between 22 March 2024 and 1 August 2025. The upper graph shows STILT results views per week and the lower graph shows the cumulative sum, with a total of 1685 views.

As each view covers up to one year of footprints, we can also look at the number of footprint days, consisting of eight 3-hourly footprints. Over the period of March 2024 to July 2025 in total 92 individual users viewed 1685 footprint animations.

Figure 41: The monthly number of footprint days displayed in the GHG footprint tool.

8.2.2 Model requests for the ICOS Footprint Service

Figure 42 shows the number of model runs started since June 2023. Each model run applies to a single station, the requested time period can vary between a few days and several years (up to 18 years). In autumn, there is usually an increase in usage of the footprint calculation service as soon as the model runs for the previous year are opened. In addition, there are always episodes when individual users start a large number of model runs for use in their projects.

Figure 42: Number of STILT model runs started in the ICOS footprint service between 14 June 2023 and 1 August 2025. The upper graph shows model run starts per week and the lower graph shows the cumulative sum of runs with a total of 1137 runs.

As each run can cover one or more days of footprints, we can also look at the number of footprint days. Each day calculated will produce eight 3-hourly footprints.

Figure 43: The monthly number of footprint days calculated in the GHG footprint tool

Over the full period, in total 88 individual users requested 1153 calculations of 265,966 footprint days, which corresponds to in total 2,127,728 calculated footprints.

8.2.3 Model results downloaded for the ICOS Footprint Service.

Figure 44 shows the number of model result packages downloaded since June 2023. Each package contains footprints and concentration time series for a single station and one year.

Figure 44: Number of downloads of packaged model results in the ICOS footprint service between 14 June 2023 and 1 August 2025. The upper graph shows downloads per week and the lower graph shows the cumulative sum of package downloads with a total of 485 downloads (until 23 April 2025). Note the maximum of 219 downloads in one single week of August 2024.

As each download can cover one or more days of footprints, we can also look at the number of footprint days downloaded. Each day in the download archive will consist of eight 3-hourly footprints

Figure 45: The monthly number of footprint days downloaded from the GHG footprint tool (until 23 April 2025)

Over the full period, in total 53 individual users requested through 485 download requests 219,862 footprint days, which corresponds to in total 1,758,896 footprints.

8.2.4 Scientific papers

Publications using the ICOS STILT Footprint Tool for GHG, since 2023:

1. Cristofanelli, P., Trisolino, P., Calzolari, F., Busetto, M., Calidonna, C. R., Amendola, S., Arduini, J., Fratticioli, C., Hundal, R. A., Maione, M., Marcucci, F., Marinoni, A., Montaguti, S., Renzi, L., Roccatto, F., Bonasoni, P., Putero, D.: Influence of wildfire emissions to carbon dioxide (CO₂) observed at the Mt. Cimone station (Italy, 2165 m asl): A multi-year investigation, *Atmospheric Environment*, 330, 120577, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2024.120577>, 2024.
2. Fratticioli, C., Trisolino, P., Maione, Calzolari, F., Calidonna, C., Biron, D., Amendola, S., Steinbacher, M., Cristofanelli, P.: Continuous atmospheric in-situ measurements of the CH₄/CO ratio at the Mt. Cimone station (Italy, 2165 m a.s.l.) and their possible use for estimating regional CH₄ emissions, *Environmental Research*, 232, 116343, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116343>. 2023.
3. Gachkivskyi, M., Karstens, U., Fischer, B., Kubistin, D., Müller-Williams, J., Lindauer, M., and Levin, I.: Radon-222 monitoring at German ICOS atmosphere stations, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2024-551>, accepted, 2025.

4. Lapenna, E., Buono, A., Mauceri, A., Zaccardo, I., Cardellicchio, F., D'Amico, F., Laurita, T., Amodio, D., Colangelo, C., Di Fiore, G., Gorga, A., Ripepi, E., De Benedictis, F., Pirelli, S., Capozzo, L., Lapenna, V., Pappalardo, G., Trippetta, S., & Mona, L.: ICOS Potenza (Italy) Atmospheric Station: A New Spot for the Observation of Greenhouse Gases in the Mediterranean Basin, *Atmosphere*, 16, 57, <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos16010057>, 2025.
5. Storm, I., Karstens, U., D'Onofrio, C., Vermeulen, A., and Peters, W.: A view of the European carbon flux landscape through the lens of the ICOS atmospheric observation network, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 23, 4993–5008, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-23-4993-2023>, 2023.
6. Storm, I., Karstens, U., D'Onofrio, C., Vermeulen, A., Hammer, S., Super, I., Glauch, T., and Peters, W.: Monitoring CO₂ in diverse European cities: Highlighting needs and challenges through characterisation, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-63>, in review, 2025.
7. Yver-Kwok, C., Ramonet, M., Rivier, L., Lian, J., Grossi, C., Curcoll, R., Kikaj, D., Chung, E., and Karstens, U.: Six years of greenhouse gas fluxes at Saclay, France, estimated with the Radon Tracer Method, *EGUsphere* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-3107>, 2024.
8. Zanchetta, A., Kooijmans, L. M. J., van Heuven, S., Scifo, A., Scheeren, H. A., Mammarella, I., Karstens, U., Ma, J., Krol, M., and Chen, H.: Sources and sinks of carbonyl sulfide inferred from tower and mobile atmospheric observations in the Netherlands, *Biogeosciences*, 20, 3539–3553, <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-20-3539-2023>, 2023.

8.3 Feedback from users on the ICOS footprint analysis

Feedback on the service is provided in several ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Through the general feedback form

This compiles the feedback given from the entire project.

8.3.1 User panel on the ICOS footprint analysis

Three feedback meetings with the User Panel of the footprint service were held during the project. These meetings provided a forum for users to share their experiences and provide valuable feedback that led to further improvements and consolidation of the service.

In the first feedback meeting, held in September 2023, users proposed clearer navigation links between the results viewer and the calculation tool to improve workflow efficiency. Participants noted that the map displaying available data had become cluttered due to the growing number of requests. The introduction of filtering options, e.g., by length of available time series, presence of observations, station type (mountain or surface), and ICOS versus non-ICOS stations was suggested. Concerns were raised regarding the visibility of other users' email addresses in the calculation queue, prompting a request for enhanced privacy measures. Detail of the feedback is available in Milestone MS5.4 section 1.3: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/11/atmo-access-milestone-20-v2.1.pdf>

In the second feedback meeting, held in in April 2024, feedback focused on improvements of the user support, such as guidance on how to acknowledge the project and the services, traceability of results via PIDs, and adding scientific use case examples in the user guide. The user panel also encouraged continued promotion of the footprint service at conferences and workshops, possibly with hands-on sessions. Details of the feedback is available in Milestone MS5.5 section " ICOS Footprint Tool (GHG)": <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2024/07/MS21-Feedback-meeting-2-with-user-panel-discussion-of-updates.pdf>

The third feedback meeting, held in March 2025, underscored the scientific value of the service. Users expressed strong appreciation for its role in their research and emphasized the importance of ensuring the seamless continuation of the service beyond the project's duration. Details of the feedback is available in Milestone MS5.6 section " ICOS Footprint Tool (GHG) ": <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2025/03/ATMO-ACCESS-WP5-S22-Feedback-meeting-3-with-user-panel-discussion-of-updates.pdf>

8.3.2 Response on feedback form related to ICOS footprint analysis

Figures 46 through 50 provide an overview of user feedback and evaluations related to the ICOS footprint analysis. In Figure 46, the user rated the functionality and relevance of the service, with responses indicating "OK" to "Very satisfied" ratings across various aspects. Figure 47 reflects the user's willingness to recommend the service to a colleague, with a very high rating provided. In Figure 48, the user indicated a preference for training resources such as e-learning tutorials. Figure 49 highlights the user's positive evaluation of the ICOS footprint analysis and Figure 50 outlines the perceived benefits, such as saving time and scientific and technical support.

Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used

4 answers

Figure 46: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used".

Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?

3 answers

Figure 47: Answer to the question "Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?".

Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

3 answers

Figure 48: Answer to the question "Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?".

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

4 answers

Figure 49: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective".

Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

4 answers

Figure 50: Answer to the question "Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt".

9 IAGOS Footprint analysis service for tropospheric vertical profiles

The IAGOS footprint analysis service combines the viewer of FLEXPART footprints and modelled SOFT-IO CO₂ contributions and allows users to explore tropospheric vertical profiles of carbon monoxide mixing ratios (measured by IAGOS) in conjunction with source attribution data (calculated using the SOFT-IO model). The vertical profiles are from airports visited by commercial aircrafts equipped with IAGOS' instrumentation. The SOFT-IO model is based on the coupling of FLEXPART backward footprint (with the receptor points located along the profile) with emission inventory databases. The service provides a visualization of the above-mentioned data via a simple, attractive user interface. Figure 51 shows the IAGOS footprints viewer page where users can select an airport and a date to visualize the footprints.

6 Source attribution using FlexparT and carbon monoxide emission inventories for In-situ Observation database, cf. Sauvage et al., 2017, doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-15271-2017

Figure 51: ATMO-ACCESS IAGOS footprints viewer Starting page (link: <https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-footprint/>).

9.1 Updates throughout the project

For the entire duration of the project, numerous suggestions expressed in the user feedback were implemented and resulted in the service improvement:

- Implementation of a time filter
- Dropdown list with stations has now a better support for the search via keyboard
- Feedback button added

- SOFT-IO model data (CO contribution) issued from CAMS-GLOB-ANT emission inventory added
- Data used by the service are now updated daily

9.2 Statistics on use of the IAGOS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the IAGOS footprint analysis service are tracked in several ways. Firstly, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then via the number of users to the IAGOS footprint analysis web-service itself, and lastly via the number of requests through the service. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (as described in subsection 4.2.2) and visits to the webpage itself gives an indication of the number of people going directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. The statistics are available since June 2023 until August 1st, 2025.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
IAGOS Footprint analysis service	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to viewer	IP-based
	Requests	Footprints displayed in viewer	Counted per display event

Table 14: Overview of usage metrics IAGOS Footprint analysis service, including counting rules and limitations.

9.2.1 Usage metrics for the IAGOS footprint analysis service

The IAGOS footprint analysis usage can be gauged by the number of people accessing the service. Figure 52 shows the number of unique (one unique IP address per day) visits over time. The total number of unique visits is 656 for the period June 22, 2023, to August 1, 2025, where the high peak at around 26th of September most likely is when the first user panel was held. The average number of visits is around 28 visits a month since the service has been released.

Footprints service - Visits

Figure 52: Number of visits over time - IAGOS Footprints viewer service from June 22, 2023 to August 1, 2025.

9.2.2 Model visualization requests for the IAGOS footprint analysis service

The number of requests is the number of footprints displayed. Figure 53 shows the number of footprints displayed over time.

Footprints service - Requests

Figure 53: Number of footprints displayed over time – IAGOS Footprints viewer service from June 22, 2023, to August 1, 2025.

The total number of footprints displayed for the IAGOS footprints viewer is 11,514 for the period June 22, 2023, to August 1, 2025. On average, 97 footprints were displayed for each user. The average number of requests is around 480 requests a month since the service has been released.

9.3 Feedback from users on the IAGOS footprint analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided through the user's panel meeting every six months. This compiles the feedback given from the entire project.

9.3.1 User panel on the IAGOS footprint analysis

The first Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the footprint service took place in September 2023 and a second one in April 2024, lastly in March 2025. General feedback was very positive about the main features of the service. The main feedback from the last meeting was to facilitate the user experience and to provide download to the data displayed. The service has been updated accordingly to the feedback in ergonomics. This download feature will be implemented but after the end of the project.

More details on the feedback are available in Milestones 20, 20 and 22 (Feedback meetings with user panel, discussion of updates, <https://www.atmo-access.eu/deliverables-and-milestones/>)

9.3.2 Response on feedback form related to the IAGOS footprint analysis service

The general feedback form received only one response related to the IAGOS footprint analysis service, and the corresponding answer can be seen in Table 15.

Please evaluate the online service you have used	
Information about the service offered	Satisfied
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	Very satisfied
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	Satisfied
Did the service comply with your expectations?	Satisfied
Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective	4
Shortly comment the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt	Saving time, scientific and technical support, ready-to-use graphics
Lastly, do you have any further comments/suggestions for improvement?	n/a

Table 15: Answer to the general feedback form on the IAGOS footprint service.

10 Online training services

Three types of training resources have been developed within the framework of the ATMO-ACCESS project: a **Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)** 'Atmospheric Research Infrastructures: Sharing the Future of Our Atmosphere', a series of **tutorial videos**, and the **serious game** 'What's Going on in the Air?'. Each resource has been made publicly available to a broad audience (through various ways: ATMO-ACCESS website or VA portal, direct links to a platform). A short description of each resource is available in [D10.5 report](#) and their detailed content is given in the [D4.4 deliverable](#).

10.1 Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)

10.1.1 Description of service

The ATMO-ACCESS Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), *Atmospheric Research Infrastructures: Sharing the Future of Our Atmosphere*, is a free, two-week course addressing air pollution and climate change challenges. It explores the work of ACTRIS, IAGOS, and ICOS and is suitable for anyone with a basic understanding of general chemistry and an undergraduate-level background in science. The course is available in English, with subtitles in multiple languages (English, French, Greek, Portuguese, Spanish, German; and simplified Chinese for the 2nd edition). Participants are expected to dedicate 2–2.5 hours per week but can adjust their pace. They can focus on key topics or explore additional materials for deeper learning. Multiple-choice quizzes enable self-assessment and certification via an open badge system.

The 1st edition (Jan 20 to Feb 16, 2025) and 2nd edition (May 12 to June 9, 2025) were hosted on the [FUN platform](#), with detailed reports ([D4.3](#) and [D4.4](#)) on course improvements and user feedback. This report provides a statistical analysis and summary of feedback from both editions, based on the participants' profiles completed at the time they register on the FUN platform (where available) and on two questionnaires: one at the beginning of the MOOC to better investigate their expectations, and one at the end to collect their feedback after completing the MOOC. Additionally, there was the general feedback form (see Appendix 11) for those who accessed the MOOC through the ATMO-ACCESS VA portal (§9.1.2). All further statistics and analysis (§9.1.3-9.1.8) have been gathered from the FUN platform (participants' profiles and MOOC specific surveys).

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
MOOC	MOOC Participants	Registered learners per course edition	Count based on FUN platform registrations
	MOOC Completion	Participants obtaining success badge	Passing grade ≥67%

Table 16: Overview of usage metrics to MOOC, including counting rules and limitations.

10.1.2 Response on feedback form related to MOOC through the ATMO-ACCESS portal

The general feedback form received only one response related to MOOC - Massive Open Online Courses, and the corresponding answer can be seen in Table 17.

Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used	
Information about the service offered	Very satisfied
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	Very satisfied
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	Very satisfied
Did the service comply with your expectations?	Very satisfied
Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?	5 - Certainly!
Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?	Videos, e-learning tutorials (with examples)
Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective	5
Shortly comment the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt	Saving time, Scientific and technical support
Lastly, do you have any further comments/suggestions for improvement?	n/a

Table 17: Answer to the general feedback form on MOOC - Massive Open Online Courses

10.1.3 Number of participants and global reach

The course has achieved significant international reach. The first edition attracted **811 participants** from **75 countries**, while the second edition attracted **518 participants** from **64 countries**, demonstrating the course's broad relevance and appeal. The figure below shows key information extracted from the FUN profiles of enrolled participants (where available), while a more detailed breakdown of the participants' countries for both editions is provided in the Annex (§14.1). Europe was the main residence continent of the registered participants (65-70%; 26 countries) with a large proportion of French residents (45% in the 1st edition, decreasing to 36% in the 2nd one). Africa accounted for 15-16% of learners (25 countries), followed by Asia (7-10%; 11 countries). Notably, China became the second largest country of enrolment for the

2nd edition, when subtitles in simplified Chinese were added. America (4-6%; 9 countries) and Oceania (Australia) were less represented.

Figure 54: Summary of key information concerning the origin of the enrolled participants in the MOOC's two editions

10.1.4 Participants' level of education and gender/age diversity

The MOOC attracted a highly educated and diverse audience, signalling significant interest in research infrastructures (RIs). The analysis of the **635 participants' profiles** that were completed **revealed strong academic backgrounds**. For the 1st edition, 102 participants hold a Bachelor's degree, 309 have a Master's degree, and 134 have a Doctorate, while for the 2nd one, 82 hold a Bachelor's degree, 184 a Master's, and 102 a Doctorate out of the 433 respondents, thus 19, 42 and 24% respectively. This suggests the course engaged skilled professionals and researchers, presenting an opportunity to enhance research capabilities.

In both editions, the course attracted **a balanced gender representation**. In the first edition, of the 631 profiles for which this information was available, **46% were female and 53% were male**. In the second edition, this balance continued with **43% female and 56% male** out of 428 total participant profiles.

Participants were encouraged to answer the **initial survey** in the first two weekly messages. They could access it anytime in the 'Read this first!' section of the MOOC. We collected **57 and 33 answers** for the 1st and 2nd editions of the initial survey, respectively, corresponding to about 7% of the enrolled participants. The **final surveys** (both for FUN and for ATMO-ACCESS) were available from the start in the 'Ending this MOOC' section, and advertised four times from the 2nd weekly message to the end. **111 and 64 replies** were recorded for the 1st and 2nd editions of the ATMO-ACCESS survey, respectively, corresponding to about 13% of the enrolled participants.

Compared to their share in the participants' profiles, women participants answered the initial and final surveys embedded into the MOOC significantly more than their male counterparts. This effect was observed in both editions. Questionnaire respondents were also slightly younger than those in the participant profiles, with an average birth year difference of about 5 years. The level of education remained representative across all surveys. Detailed statistics are given in the table below.

Edition	Participants' profiles		Initial survey		Final survey	
	1 st	2 nd	1 st	2 nd	1 st	2 nd
# Enrolled participants	811	518	811	518	811	518
Level of education n =	635 (78.3%)	433 (83.6%)	56 (6.9%)	33 (6.4%)	88 (10.9%)	58 (11.2%)
Bachelor degree	102 (16.0%)	82 (19.0%)	10 (17.9%)	7 (21.2%)	19 (21.6%)	10 (17.2%)
Master degree	309 (48.7%)	184 (42.5%)	28 (50.0%)	15 (45.5%)	43 (48.9%)	31 (53.4%)
PhD degree	134 (21.1%)	102 (23.6%)	13 (23.2%)	10 (30.3%)	24 (27.3%)	12 (20.7%)
Other	90 (14.2%)	65 (15.0%)	5 (8.9%)	1 (3.0%)	2 (2.3%)	5 (8.6%)
Gender n =	631 (77.8%)	428 (82.6%)	57 (7.0%)	33 (6.4%)	95 (11.7%)	57 (11.0%)
F	288 (45.6%)	181 (42.2%)	32 (56.1%)	21 (63.6%)	48 (50.5%)	31 (54.4%)
M	333 (52.8%)	237 (55.4%)	22 (38.6%)	12 (36.4%)	46 (48.4%)	26 (45.6%)
Other/NA	10 (0.016%)	10 (0.023%)	3 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Year of birth n =	593 (73.1%)	399 (77.0%)	56 (6.9%)	33 (6.4%)	89 (11.0%)	56 (10.8%)
Minimum	1943	1955	1965	1971	1953	1964
Maximum	2008	2007	2005	2002	2006	2004
Mean	1986	1988	1991	1993	1990	1993
Median	1989	1990	1994	1995	1994	1995

Table 18: Summary of key information concerning the level of education, gender and age diversity of the enrolled participants in the MOOC's two editions depending on the information source.

10.1.5 Audience attraction and scientific background

The MOOC successfully attracted its audience through various communication channels. Promotional materials, including a teaser and both printed and electronic flyers, were distributed via social media, the three RI newsletters, the YouTube channels of both the ATMO-ACCESS project and the RIs, and the FUN MOOC platform. In the first edition, a dedicated article on the FUN MOOC platform was particularly effective for communication within France. To analyse the success of these efforts, a specific question was included in the initial FUN questionnaire: "*How did you hear about this MOOC?*". The following Figure presents the relative attraction sources, based on the **40 and 33 responses** received in the initial survey for the 1st and the 2nd edition, respectively.

Figure 55: Relative contributions of the attraction sources by MOOC participants for the 1st and 2nd editions

The initial survey question, "*What is your 'level' on the subject of this MOOC?*", revealed that the course engaged a diverse audience, attracting **beginners, and researchers with advanced knowledge** on the topic of atmospheric RIs, with more advanced and expert participants for the 2nd edition. The complete analysis of the 40 responses from the first edition and 34 from the second is presented in the graph below.

Figure 56: Relative contributions of the level of prior knowledge of the topic by MOOC participants for the 1st and 2nd editions

10.1.6 Visibility

The videos produced for the two MOOC editions have received **a total of around 4,700 views**. While teaser interviews and 'making-of' videos are publicly available, the main video courses for weeks 1 and 2 are exclusive to registered participants. For the second edition, the MOOC tutorial, the video on atmospheric simulation chambers and the tutorial on the Time Series Analysis tool were added. Additionally, the latter video was made publicly available on the VA portal only after the 2nd edition of the MOOC had ended, enabling the number of views during the MOOC to be counted.

More details and the specific number of views are presented in the table below.

Video topic		1 st edition	2 nd edition
Teaser		200	21
MOOC Tutorial		n/a	150
Week 1	Air pollution vs. Climate change	466	251
	Aerosols and Clouds	425	230
	Trace gases and Greenhouse gases	300	175
	Atmospheric Research Infrastructures	281	124
Week 2	ACTRIS	259	128
	Meet ACTRIS	124	79
	IAGOS	222	122
	Meet IAGOS	66	55
	ICOS	189	88
	Meet ICOS	60	40
	The workflow and benefits of a coordinated approach	162	81
	Atmospheric Simulation Chambers	n/a	143
Tutorial Timeseries Analysis		n/a	130
Making of		58	27
Total views		2,812	1,844

Table 19: YouTube views of the MOOC videos

10.1.7 Completion rates

The course has achieved **high completion rates** in both editions. In the 1st edition, **21.5%** of participants earned a success badge, with **174 participants successfully** completing the final graded quiz. Of the **212 participants who attempted the quiz, 82%** (174 people) achieved the passing grade of 67%. In the 2nd edition, **16.8%** of participants, or **87 people**, successfully completed the course. A remarkable **83% of the 105** participants who took the final graded quiz achieved a passing grade. These results highlight the engagement and motivation of learners, signalling a completion rate much higher than the usual 10% for this type of course.

10.1.8 User feedback

At the end of the MOOC, participants completed a 15-question follow-up survey, with the questions listed in the Annex of [D4.3](#). In the 1st MOOC edition, the questionnaire was answered by **111 participants (13.7 % of the 811 enrolled)** and in the 2nd edition, by **64 (12.4 % of the 518 enrolled)**. The survey analysis focused on participants' satisfaction regarding their expectations and the quality of the material provided. The main conclusions of this analysis are presented in the following table. The numbers represent the percentage of participants who reported being either satisfied or very satisfied with each specific criterion.

Satisfaction rate* (%)	1 st edition (n = 111)	2 nd edition (n = 64)
Course relevance	93.5	97.6
Meeting participant needs		
calendar	83.5	90.6
grading	84.5	90.3
pedagogical design	94.3	89.1
Content quality		
videos	90.6	85.5
quizzes	87.7	81.3
Interest of		
interactive content	84.7	87.5
interviews	77.7	87.1
additional materials	85.5	86.9
Subtitle usefulness	69.1	60.9

Table 20: Summary of key information concerning the participants' satisfaction in the MOOC's two editions. * From the participants who answered the specific questions

All criteria scored satisfaction rates of over 80%, except for the interviews in the 1st edition. In the 2nd, the interview videos were more highly rated (+10%), possibly because they were directly linked to the relevant RI, and a new video containing interviews with several researchers about atmospheric simulation chambers was added.

For the 1st edition, subtitles were considered 'extremely useful' by 28.7% of respondents and 'useful' by 41.7%. For the second edition (with the addition of Simplified Chinese), these figures were 18.8% and 42.2%, respectively. These results highlight the importance of subtitles in enhancing learner experience, suggesting that further investment in multilingual subtitle options, especially in widely spoken or strategically targeted languages, could significantly increase the course's accessibility, attractiveness, and global reach.

The final survey ended with three open questions:

- 1) Which part of the MOOC did you like most and why?
- 2) Would you like to propose ideas to improve the course?
- 3) Would you like to add any general remarks?

Question 1 gathered 86 and 39 replies for the 1st and 2nd editions, respectively; question 2, 54 and 14 replies; question 3, 40 and 15 replies.

In the first edition, participants strongly indicated their appreciation for the interactive videos, the course structure, interviews, descriptions of the different RIs, interactive links, and quizzes. In the second edition, participants also highlighted several new additions, including the 'How to access and process data' tutorial, enhanced interactivity (interactions, questions, etc), and the Atmospheric Simulation Chamber video-course. Answers to Question 1 can be found in Appendix §14.2.1.

Question 2 provided valuable key findings and significant insights. Regarding the 1st MOOC edition answers, among the most frequent requests were calls for more activities, interactions, and guidance on how to access and process data. To address this feedback several crucial improvements for the 2nd MOOC edition were performed. A tutorial video for the Timeseries analysis tool was developed to provide a step-by-step guide to data analysis, while numerous interactions and challenging activities were also added. The table below highlights some of the participants' insights from the 1st edition that directly guided and led to significant changes. A detailed list of all improvements can be found in the Annex of [D4.4](#).

How to explore data from the data or service portal? Is it possible to have videos to have an overview how it works?
All the course was very nice and the quizzes during the video help us to keep it interactive. Thanks for this. Maybe a quick reminder of all the layers of the atmosphere at the beginning of the course could be interesting to add for the future session.
Add a practical explanation on how to access the data.
I really liked knowing the different platforms, databases and sources that will be very important for my research and self-taught study.
Add links/ how to access the RIs.
Expand radiation budget and potential global warming subjects.
A few of the questions/quizzes appearing in the videos tend to be scheduled incorrectly, thus stopping the speaker before the sentence is finished.
From my humble opinion, it could be useful to know at least the main variables recorded with each equipment.
Improve the activities.
Would be interesting to know more about other services that RIs provide, except data. May be some more examples of the use of the RIs by scientists and society.
Some subtitles weren't properly aligned.
Make the quizzes tougher.
Maybe more about the different types of analytical techniques used.
Maybe more interactive ways?

Table 21: Participants needs and ideas from the 1st edition feedback survey that were taken into account in the 2nd MOOC edition

The same question was tailored also in the 2nd edition. This time, the responses provided valuable insights into the audience's learning needs, revealing key expectations and aspirations of the scientific community. Participants specifically requested **more interactions and animations**, as well as some **remote access** activities, such as group discussions or collaborative projects, and live Q&A sessions. This feedback highlighted important ideas and identified gaps that can be addressed with new pedagogical material and future course improvements. The following table presents an overview of these expectations and needs.

Offering more interactive activities, like group discussions or live Q&A sessions, could increase engagement and provide more opportunities for students to collaborate and learn from one another.
A technical course.
Introducing more interactive activities, such as group discussions or collaborative projects, could enhance engagement and encourage peer learning.
Expanding the "scientific" topics, still keeping a section on RIs but less predominant.
Maybe some specific examples of study for each RI.
I think that more courses like those from the first week are needed to be included!
Information on the processes taking place in the atmosphere in a little more detail and on a very concrete level (giving concrete examples).
Examples of application of methodologies

It could be interesting a section on measures to improve air pollution and climate change, highlighting synergies and possible trade-offs.
All was perfect, only add more animations in your videos.
I would like you to do virtual sessions or a competition to receive training in air quality observation topics.
A part in real time for questions and discuss is needed, in order to be more interactive.
More interviews of young researchers working in IRs to attract students.
Sometimes the speaker and the slides go a little bit too fast, I had to pause many times and go backwards to have time to take notes
Subtitles are useful especially as most of the trainers aren't native English speakers, it can be sometimes hard to understand.
In my opinion, there was too much high-level information coming at a too high speed. I had difficulties to process everything so quickly. A lot of a priori knowledge was already required to be able to follow this course.

Table 22: Participants' expectations and needs to be addressed in future virtual educational material

In the last survey open question, participants were asked to add any general remarks. The feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with mainly congratulations and appreciation comments. Main answers and remarks are presented in Appendix §14.2.2.

10.2 Tutorial videos

10.2.1 Description of service

In addition to a specific tutorial to guide participants in the MOOC for the 2nd edition, three tutorial videos (as open access educational e-learning tools) were specifically developed to meet diverse needs and fill existing gaps within the atmospheric RI community. The main objective of the tutorial videos is to test new ways of training beyond the remote and/or physical access. Suitable for anyone with a basic understanding in atmospheric science, they provide **easy, quick and effective digital learning** covering a broad spectrum of **applications and topics** in the field. The tutorials are available in English, with subtitles in multiple languages (English, French, Greek, Portuguese, Spanish, German, and simplified Chinese). ATMO-ACCESS [website](#) host the interactive videos, while simple videos (without interactions) are provided directly on [YouTube](#).

Discover the three ATMO-ACCESS tutorial videos!

High-resolution online quantification of trace metals in particulate matter using the Xact®
Instructor & Presenter: Kanneh Wadinga Fomba
 Explore the Xact instrument inside & outside
 Uncover its power with clear step-by-step guidance of its intuitive software

TROPOS
Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research

A Step-by-Step Tutorial Video for the Time Series Analysis in ATMO-ACCESS
Presenter: Hannah Clark
 Dive into the Time Series Analysis service
 Learn how to effectively access & analyse the RIs observational data

Laero
Laboratoire d'Aérodynamique

VolcPlume Portal tutorial video
Instructor & Presenter: Marie Boichu
 Unleash the power of the VolcPlume platform
 Detect & analyse volcanic plumes with clear instructions & a real-case study integrating satellite, ground-based remote sensing & in situ observations

LOA
Laboratoire d'Observatoire Atmosphérique

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement N° 101008004

Figure 57: General overview of the tutorials' topics

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
Tutorial videos	Video views	Number of views per tutorial video	Includes ATMO-ACCESS website and YouTube views

Table 23: Overview of usage metrics to tutorial videos, including counting rules and limitations.

10.2.2 Usage metrics

The use of the tutorial videos was tracked in several ways, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS website, and via the number of views of each video on the YouTube platform.

Tutorial video	Title	Online availability	Page views on ATMO-ACCESS website (on Aug. 27th)	Views on YouTube (on Sep. 12th)	Feedback number (on Sep. 12th)
Xact (625i Ambient Continuous Multi-Metals Monitor)	High resolution online quantification of trace metals in particulate matter using the Xact	April 2025	159	246	15
TSA (Time Series Analysis)	A step-by-step tutorial video for the time series analysis in ATMO-ACCESS	May 2025	159	244	18
VolcPlume	VolcPlume Portal tutorial video	June 2025	168	133	7

Table 24: Usage metrics and feedback number for each tutorial video

10.2.3 User feedback and survey analysis

Each tutorial video ended with a link to an optional questionnaire using the open tool Framafoms. The table above indicates the number of feedback received at the beginning of September 2025. Although the number of views was high, the feedback received was very little. Probably some viewers watch the tutorials through YouTube (and not the interactive videos through the ATMO-ACCESS site) so they were unable to click the link interactions and visit the Framafom questionnaires. To address this, we've now (beginning of September 2025) added the questionnaire links to the YouTube video descriptions, ensuring all viewers can easily provide their feedback.

The following graph shows the residence country of the 37 total respondents. Except for one viewer from Argentina and another from China, all respondents were from Europe. For the Xact tutorial, 15 viewers replied, with the majority from Romania (4), France (2), Spain (2) and Czech (2). The TSA tutorial received 18 responses, with Germany accounting for the highest number (4) of replies followed by Romania, France and Spain with 3. The VolcPlume tutorial had the fewest respondents, 7 in total, with Romania and France in the top two with 3 and 2 feedback respectively.

Figure 58: Country of residence for the 40 respondents. This includes 15 for Xact, 18 for TSA, and 7 for VolcPlume.

For the Xact and VolcPlume tutorials, more than the half of the respondents were from academia. In contrast, the TSA questionnaire received no responses from students, despite being integrated into the MOOC watched by many. Regarding familiarity with the subject, the majority of respondents across the tutorials reported being "neutral to unfamiliar," meaning they had heard of the topic but had some to no prior experience. Only the 33, 25, and 28 % of the respondents were familiar with Xact instrument, TSA tool and VolcPlume platform respectively.

Figure 59: Profile analysis of the 40 respondents.

Overall, respondents were highly satisfied with TSA and VolcPlume tutorials, consistently rating them as **very useful**, with VolcPlume receiving the highest score 71%. Additionally, around **57%** of all respondents indicated they would **definitely recommend** the tutorials. Subtitle utility varied across the tutorials. Most respondents found the **subtitles helpful, more than 72% for Xact and VolcPlume**. Notably, 50% of TSA viewers reported not needing them, likely due to the native-speaking narrator.

Figure 60: Answers to the questions: "How useful did you find the content of the video for your scientific or professional work?", "Would you recommend this tutorial to others?", "The video is subtitled in several languages. How useful were the subtitles for you personally?".

Satisfaction with the video and audio quality was high across the board. The tutorials' pacing was also highly rated, with the Xact tutorial receiving the highest score at 93% and VolcPlume the lowest at 71%. The majority of respondents were also satisfied with the depth of the content, interactivity, and subtitle translation. These aspects received satisfaction rates 67, 87, and 93% for Xact and 83, 72 and 83% for TSA respectively. The VolcPlume tutorial also performed well, with 71, 57 and 71% of respondents expressing satisfaction on these indicators.

Figure 61: Satisfaction rates for several indicators

The open-ended question "If you have any additional comments or suggestions for topics you'd like to see in future tutorials, please write them below," yielded three responses for the Xact and eight for TSA video. No comment for the VOLPLUME platform tutorial was provided. The detailed replies are shown in Appendix 15, while a summary is given below.

The Xact comments highlighted the need for more advanced training on topics such as: X-ray fluorescence principles, calibration and maintenance, offline analysis, post-processing data, and a training room with ADAPT hands-on. This feedback is valuable and could be useful to develop a more advanced, longer tutorial for new instrumentation. Responders highlight the need of more tutorial videos on instrumental demonstration. The comments for the TSA tutorial were generally positive. Two respondents mentioned a problem with the links, as they were not clickable for viewers watching on YouTube. To fix this, we've now added all relevant links to the YouTube video description. Suggestions about clarity were taken into account by adding some zoom views, while a comment on the TSA tool is going to be addressed to the tool developer. One insightful suggestion was to: *"include some scientific context and real-world applications of time series analysis, helping viewers understand why these methods matter. Adding a short section on methodological details such as basic statistical techniques for trend detection or seasonality."* This is an excellent idea that could be developed into a new, short tutorial video for this and other tools in the future.

10.3 Serious game

10.3.1 Description of service

The serious game "What's going on in the air?" provides an opportunity to enhance the player's knowledge of ground-based remote sensing using a real-world case study. In the game, the player assumes the role of a young scientist at the Atmospheric Observatory of Lille (ATOLL) in France. His task is to use real data from LIDAR and sun photometers to investigate an anomaly in aerosol measurements. The objective of this virtual training service is to provide a joyful, engaging and effective learning experience. This game, which is suitable for anyone with a basic understanding of atmospheric science, is available in English on the ATMO-ACCESS [website](#). A detailed description is provided in report [D4.4](#).

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
Serious game	Visits	Visits to the webpage hosting the serious game	Page views used as visits.

Table 25: Overview of usage metrics to the serious game, including counting rules and limitations.

10.3.2 Usage metrics

The serious game's performance was initially monitored solely through access data, with a total of **444 page views** recorded on the ATMO-ACCESS site. To gather more in-depth usage metrics, a second improved version of the game will be developed and launched in the upcoming months. It will be hosted on a permanent platform designed to capture key data points, such as player profiles, scores, and engagement time.

10.3.3 User feedback and survey analysis

An optional feedback questionnaire, created using the open-source tool Framiforms, was provided to players at the conclusion of the serious game. By early September 2025, only 22 responses had been collected, a very low number given the high volume of page views.

The following graph illustrates the geographic distribution of the 22 respondents. All participants, except for those from Aruba, Azerbaijan, and Lebanon, were from Europe. The data indicates a strong concentration in a few key countries, with France (6 respondents) and Romania (4 respondents) having the highest number of replies. This may be due to the location of the two main units of the Topical Centre for Atmospheric Remote Sensing component of ACTRIS (INOE, Romania and LOA, France).

Figure 62: Country of residence for the 22 respondents to the survey.

The majority of the 22 respondents were at an academic level (14 respondents, 64%), while 5 were students (23%). Furthermore, 17 participants (77%) reported being familiar or having basic knowledge on the topic, indicating a high level of prior understanding.

Figure 63: Profile analysis of the 22 respondents to the survey.

The serious game received high overall satisfaction ratings from respondents. The most highly rated features were the interactive challenges and short games, identified as the favourite by 77% of participants. Demonstrating the importance of interactivity and playfulness in learning. Graphics and visuals closely follow (73%) and the storyline and plot with 68%. Features such as

feedback/progress tracking (45%) and scoring/achievements (41%) received comparatively lower satisfaction scores.

Figure 64: Answers to the question: "Which gameplay features did you enjoy the most?"

The usefulness of the serious game received a perfect 100% satisfaction score from participants, while engaging content scored 95%. Satisfaction with game difficulty, game experience, and time needed was also high across the board, with all ratings above 82%. The theory and back trajectory content were also highly rated at 64%.

However, some aspects received lower scores, indicating a desire for more content and case studies. These include interactive elements (59%), remote sensing content (59%), and the integration of different types of data (41%).

Figure 65: Satisfaction rates for several game features

An open-ended question asking for comments and suggestions received 10 responses from players. The detailed replies are provided in Appendix 16. The feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with 6 of the 10 comments congratulating the game developers on the serious game's quality. Several key findings and suggestions for improvement emerged from the comments. For instance, players requested more detailed explanations for the graphs and suggested adding the correct answers within the game itself. These valuable suggestions will be incorporated into the second, improved edition of the game.

Interestingly, several comments mentioned the "Run in the Dust Storm" mini-game. A few players questioned its usefulness, despite the fact that this segment was designed as a playful dream sequence to provide a welcome and intentional diversion from the main content with no specific educational purpose and to separate the two scientific days.

11 Conclusion and next steps

This deliverable concludes the reporting of user statistics and feedback for the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access services. The VA Portal and its associated tools have achieved steady engagement, with growing numbers of users, curated datasets, model runs and scientific publications demonstrating their use and scientific relevance. At the same time, collecting feedback has required high effort for low reward, with only limited responses despite repeated outreach. Nevertheless, the feedback received has been valuable for improving usability,

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

documentation and functionality. The long-term strategy for the future use of these services, and their best application for science, management and outreach, is described in [Deliverable D10.3](#).

12 Appendix: General Feedback Form - questions

Feedback questionnaire for users of ATMO-ACCESS online services

You have used free services available from this site: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>. To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring.

Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

Note that you should complete this form separately for every service instance that you want to provide feedback on!

* indikerer at spørsmålet er obligatorisk

1. Privacy notice *

The ATMO-ACCESS privacy notice can be accessed at this link: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/atmo-access-privacy-policy/>

All replies will be treated in the strictest confidence. The information given will only be used for monitoring and assessment purposes in accordance with the European [General Data Protection Regulation](#).

Merk av for alt som passer

I agree with the ATMO-ACCESS privacy policy and terms of use

2. Do you agree to be contacted for further feedback or to be informed of further improvements? (If yes, please add your email address below!) *

Merk av for alt som passer

Yes

No

3. Email address

4. First name

5. Last name

6. Home institution

7. Your background and position *

Check all that apply.

Merk av for alt som passer

- Academic (post-doc, researcher, lecturer)
- Student (undergraduate, PhD)
- Project leader
- Air quality network and/or other Research Infrastructure
- Industry
- Private enterprise
- Government Organisation
- Independent Scientist
- Andre: _____

8. How did you find out about the online services supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project? *

Merk av for alt som passer

- ATMO-ACCESS website
- Research infrastructure websites
- Direct mailing from Research Infrastructure
- Twitter
- LinkedIn
- Other social media
- Information recieved by colleagues/personal contacts
- Information recieved at event
- Andre: _____

9. Service accessed *

If you have tried more than one of these, please complete the entire form once for each service you want to give feedback on.

Markér bare én oval.

- Homeless Data Portal
- Footprint - Aerosol distribution and source analysis
- Footprint - Greenhouse gases
- Footprint - Tropospheric vertical gradients
- Time Series Analysis
- MOOC - Massive Open Online Courses
- Helpdesk for any of the services

10. Please evaluate the **access** to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access> *

Markér bare én oval per rad

	Not relevant	Poor	OK	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Publicity and information on the access portal before login	<input type="radio"/>				
System for registration and authentication to get access to the service	<input type="radio"/>				
Publicity and information on the access portal after login	<input type="radio"/>				

11. Please evaluate the **functionality & relevance** of the online service you used *

Markér bare én oval per rad

	Not relevant	Poor	OK	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Information about the service offered	<input type="radio"/>				
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	<input type="radio"/>				
Did the service comply with your expectations?	<input type="radio"/>				

12. Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague? *

This mainly concerns the scientific usefulness

Markér bare én oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Def Certainly!

13. Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

Merk av for alt som passer

- Videos
- e-learning tutorials (with examples)
- Interactive webinars
- In-person training (e.g. at conferences)
- Library of scientific use cases
- Written documentation
- Andre: _____

14. Please feel free to share any other comments/suggestions about the service you used!

15. Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective *
This covers both the access process and the online services

Markér bare én oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Ver: Excellent

16. If your evaluation is ≤ 2 , we appreciate if you can briefly explain why:

17. Shortly comment on the **benefits** of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

Merk av for alt som passer

- Saving time
- Scientific and technical support
- Easy data access
- Immediate access to the results / interactive analysis
- Ready-to-use graphics
- Andre: _____

18. Do you have any further comments/suggestions about the Virtual Access setup?

13 Appendix: General Feedback Form – free text answers

This Appendix compiles the free text comments and suggestions from users given in the general feedback form.

Homeless Data Portal | Free text comments and suggestions

I try to submit 2 data slots, one was for the storage of the existing ACTRIS variables - this went very smoothly, exchange with data centre unit (ARES) was perfect, fast efficient. For the other data slot - the variables were NOT variables on any of the 3 infrastructures, the process of publication was very heavy, with delayed communication, difficulty to fill in the request, messages bouncing between HDP and ARES, after several months I withdraw the data publication and published elsewhere. So to me HDP is not good to handle unexpected data and it is excellent to handle the classical variables of the three RIs. This should be communicated to the users clearly, and for this moment it is not.

Wish the data from the old version was completely moved to the beta version. I could not access the old data anymore after the portal switched or switch between the old version and the beta version.

Time Series Analysis | Free text comments and suggestions

Worked Examples required for adequate training

please add more ACTRIS data and date for aerosols as well, need more data availability

It is a very nice time series analysis service, with access to a number of atmospheric components and meteorological parameters from different research infrastructures. There are different options for data selection and aggregation. The user can produce and download different kinds of figures, including histograms, box plots, time series and scatter plots of different fields. Moreover, the service provides three different options for trend calculations based on both parametric and non-parametric methods.

The plots are good and at this moment the only feature that is missing is the possibility of downloading the processed (e.g. daily, monthly, etc.) data. That could be very useful for additional scientific analyses, or to obtain time series that can be further analysed in statistics lectures as well as by Bachelor and Master theses. With that feature implemented I would rate the question ""Did the service comply with your expectations?"" with a 5.

Overall, it is very good. As I said, when the users have access to the data that they are plotting (e.g. as ascii files) then this portal will be great.

The tool is well done and would be perfect if the time series are good ones. Here some comments:

- there is no documentation on the methodology. E.g. how are the trend (and particularly the Mann-Kendall and Theil-Sen slope applied? Is any pre-whitening method applied? What is the differences between the Mann-Kendall and Theil-Sen slope methods, since MK should give the statistically significant and the Theil-Sen slope, the slope? How are the time series deseasonalised? etc

- Trend analysis can only be applied on homogeneous time series. The time series tool allows to choose part of the time series which seem homogeneous for the analysis. It would however be very nice to have also method to test the homogeneity of the time series.

- I chose aerosol time series from two stations. Since some time series are stored in several parts in Ebas, the merging of the different parts is not possible prior to the trend analysis.
- I test the Jungfraujoch data that I know quite well. There is 2 instruments measuring the absorption coefficient. It is not possible to know from which instrument come the selected time series.
- Concerning the previous questions in this feedback tool, you should differentiate between the functionality/conviviality of the time series analysis tool, which I find very good, and the applied methodologies.
- finally, who develop this tool? I think that it is important to give the credit of this development to the developers.

A further information is that I published Mann-Kendall routines in R, python and matlab in github (<https://github.com/mannkendall>) that could be directly used for the MK analysis. I stay at your disposal for any information/discussion.

Hello, thanks for this very nice tool. It is very nice to access the different data bases and combine the data to produce some quick analysis. I will for sure use it in the future and suggest it to colleagues.

For further improvement, I have the following suggestions:

- it is a bit difficult to understand the time series downloaded from the ACTRIS data portal. There are overlapping time intervals, there are parameters listed that do not necessarily make sense (e.g. Why detection limit? When you want to plot NO₂ or NO_x) and the names of the ACTRIS time series are not easy to read for a user (...and I checked the data from our station). The ICOS names seemed easy to understand. I suggest this needs some improvement.
- how do I contact the tech support for the time series tool - I could not find a link.
- will there be other data bases added in the future?
- will there be other variables/parameters added in the future? E.g. NMHCs

Thanks again and I hope this nice tool will be continued, accessible and updated in the next years.

I tried to do a time series analysis of ozone data at the Jungfraujoch station - selecting Jungfraujoch ACTRIS as well as Jungfraujoch ICOS stations. I know from the ACTRIS data portal that there are Ozone FTIR data series available in the ACTRIS DC. Nevertheless, the tool gives me a warning: ""No datasets found. Change search criteria"". Why? A colleague of mine did the check independently and had the same problem.

The second question is: can the tool also be used for data that are NOT in ACTRIS, ICOS or IAGOS datacentres but of exactly the same nature - e.g., FTIR ozone data at another NDACC station that is not part of ACTRIS? Or should we then use the VRE? Or is even the VRE not applicable to such application?

thank you ! keep going

The system has very nice functionalities. If we can download the final data that are being used for the graphics that would be great (I understand that will be implemented). If possible, BL/MT/UT meteo data in the case of IAGOS would also be very valuable (for the moment only O3 and CO are available). Have you thought about using near-surface air quality data (e.g. O3, PM, etc) from EMEP or other networks? Honestly, I am not sure I will use it very regularly for my work, because I am involved in other types of projects at the moment. However, I think it will be very useful to produce plots that I can show in some lectures or for some of the students working on their Bachelor or even Msc theses.

Footprint - Greenhouse gases

Free text comments and suggestions

Thank you for this platform,

I also want to know if we can extend it for some places in Africa, I am interested to see the footprint of the Atlas MOhamed V Station which is a ICOS class 2 Station

<https://icos-atc.lsce.ipsl.fr/panelboard/AMV/>

I would like to be able to see this fingerprint, not the concentration but just the sources from where do they come

Footprint - Aerosol distribution and source analysis

Free text comments and suggestions

I used FLEXPART BC sourcemaps and highly recommend them and the FLEXPART tools in general!

The service was ok, but I think it could be improved.

14 Appendix: Homeless Data Portal - Frequently Asked Questions

What does “homeless data” refer to and who can use this service?

In the ATMO-ACCESS Project “homeless data” refers to data sets not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centres. This includes data sets from Transnational Access (TNA) activities, research campaigns and ‘short-term’ national or international research projects.

Anyone with data which falls under the classification of “homeless data”, as described above, can use the service.

Is the service free of charge?

Data curation through the ATMO-ACCESS project is free of charge to the end of the project 1st of April 2025. Curation of homeless data will also be available after the projects end, but then associated to a low cost

Will my data be associated with the term “homeless data”?

The term “homeless data” itself is only used for the portal. All data curated through the ATMO-ACCESS homeless data portal will have an “ATMO-ACCESS” tag in the data centre for the respective RIs, to be able to identify these data later. Furthermore, the data can have additional tags, associating the data to a corresponding research project selected by the user of the service.

Can I request curation for stations, instruments or methods not already in the RIs?

Yes, if it's atmospheric measurement data.

What to expect from us after submitting a request?

After submitting a request, you will be contacted by a data curator from a relevant RI about the future process. The data curator will explain the workflow at the relevant RI and guide you through the process. You will get access to tools used for data curation/submission. After submitting the data in the right format with as much metadata as possible, the data will follow the standard workflow of the RI, including quality control tests. The RI will then make the data available for end-users and assign the data set(s) DOI(s) and give you access to usage tracking tools.

What is expected by me?

It is expected that you format your data according to the needs of the relevant RI, with guidance from the data curators, and provide metadata to accompany your data set.

Which research infrastructure (RI) should I expect to be contacted by?

ACTRIS for data on reactive trace gases, cloud and aerosol particle properties.

ICOS for surface data on greenhouse gases including halocarbons.

IAGOS for data collected on moving platforms (aircraft, drones, balloons).

Are there any tools for formatting the data correctly?

Yes, you will get access to RI specific tools for data curation after requesting data and being assigned to your relevant RI(s).

What benefits are there to using the Homeless Data Portal, compared to storing the data by myself?

Storing your data in a RIs is the most efficient way to ensure long term storage of your data and promote visibility and access data for a larger research community. Using the homeless data portal makes sure these data are well documented for future use and easily available. Furthermore, you as a data provider can get access to usage tracking of your data.

Will I get DOI(s) for my data set(s) and what is a collection DOI?

A DOI is a digital identifier of an object, any object — physical, digital, or abstract. When delivering data sets through the Homeless Data Portal, each data set will be provided with a DOI by the RI. If there are several data sets, for example across different RIs, we also provide the option to get a collection DOI. A collection DOI is thus one DOI that identifies a group or collection of data that e.g. might have data across the RIs.

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

15 Appendix: MOOC enrolments per residence country and open answers

15.1 MOOC enrolments per residence country of the participants for the 1st, 2nd and both editions

Country	Edition			Country	Edition		
	1st	2nd	Both		1st	2nd	Both
Algeria	6	3	9	Japan	1	0	1
Andorra	1	0	1	Jordan	1	1	2
Argentina	5	4	9	Latvia	1	0	1
Australia	2	0	2	Lebanon	9	2	11
Austria	3	1	4	Lithuania	3	1	4
Belgium	21	5	26	Madagascar	6	4	10
Benin	6	8	14	Malaysia	0	1	1
Bolivia	1	1	2	Mali	1	0	1
Brazil	2	10	12	Mauritania	1	0	1
Burkina Faso	3	4	7	Mexico	1	2	3
Burundi	3	1	4	Morocco	28	12	40
Côte d'Ivoire	10	10	20	Nepal	2	0	2
Cambodia	1	0	1	Netherlands	2	2	4
Cameroon	3	5	8	Niger	2	0	2
Canada	8	7	15	Nigeria	1	4	5
Chad	2	0	2	Norway	1	2	3
Chile	1	2	3	Oman	0	1	1
China	12	20	32	Pakistan	5	4	9
Colombia	1	2	3	Poland	18	13	31
Comoros	1	0	1	Portugal	2	4	6
Congo	1	2	3	Romania	5	12	17
DR Congo	8	5	13	Rwanda	1	0	1
Cyprus	6	5	11	Saudi Arabia	0	1	1
Czech Republic	22	7	29	Senegal	16	11	27
Denmark	3	1	4	Singapore	0	1	1
Egypt	2	1	3	Slovakia	1	0	1
Finland	3	9	12	Slovenia	5	2	7
France	363	189	552	South Africa	6	1	7
Gabon	1	1	2	Spain	34	12	46
Germany	22	15	37	Sudan	0	1	1
Ghana	-	2	2	Sweden	1	6	7
Greece	13	15	28	Switzerland	4	4	8
Guinea	2	1	3	Thailand	1	3	4
Haiti	5	1	6	Togo	2	3	5
Hungary	2	0	2	Tunisia	10	4	14
India	17	17	34	Ukraine	2	0	2
Indonesia	3	1	4	United Kingdom	7	4	11
Iran	1	0	1	United States of America	10	2	12
Iraq	1	1	2	Vietnam	3	0	3
Ireland	6	11	17	Zimbabwe	1	1	2
Italy	17	16	33	Unknown	27	14	41
Total	811	518	1329				

Bold numbers in shaded cells: top 5 countries.

15.2 MOOC open answers

The following section presents the feedback survey responses on the open questions for the two editions. The second edition of the course was improved based on comments from the first.

15.2.1 Which part of the MOOC did you like most and why?

1 st edition	2 nd edition
The presentation of the RIs and their interactions with each other, academia, industry, society and policy makers.	From a pedagogical point of view, the videos were extremely informative and easy to understand.
The quizzes helped me a lot.	Questions
Week 1, as it gave me some very useful insights + the intermediate tests to check whether I understood everything.	The small questionnaires, activities and additional information that help integrate the information.
Course Structure and the part that talk about the RI and the question that pop out during the video that make sure I am following up with the material.	Week 2, since the theory mostly I am familiar with and now looking for new opportunities in the field, Europe feels now a very good place to start and try to stay in touch with these facilities.
Week 2, because a lot is said about methods and directions.	Climate change. It helps to understand better concerning the stratosphere.
Very comprehensive and lots of interactive resources well done.	I like the most, the video on how to access and process RI data.
Aerosols and clouds.	Dynamic videos and quizzes.
The videos and quizzes because I read the rest of the day.	The explicative course, as it has been organised so structural.
All of it	Air pollution and climate change.
Backstage :) , seriously, I did not have a lot of information about IAGOS and it helped me to explore this platform.	Info about ACTRIS and trace Gas.
I enjoyed the interactive videos and the tricky quizzes. Because they stimulated my mind and I gained new knowledge regarding atmospheric research infrastructures.	I really liked everything to be honest. The videos are helpful because I am an optical learner myself. The quizzes and the summary are fun and useful to make sure that I understood the concepts.
Research infrastructures given that my main knowledge is about ACTRIS and it allows me to know the rest.	I appreciated learning about the specific RIs and hearing from the people who work within these organisations.
The video presentation, teaching style, pop up questions and relevant links during the video.	ACTRIS presentation. Because it's more related to my work.
To see the potential practical applications.	Everything!
I liked that the MOOC interactive portions allowed me to engage in the practicality of what I am learning. It was very interesting to	I particularly enjoyed the sections on atmospheric measurement techniques and instrumentation because they provided clear

see exactly how these theoretical things translate into real-world application. The explanations of complex concepts were clear and concise; hence, I managed to catch firm understanding easily, while this course really kept me interested from the very start all the way to the end. All in all, it was a rewarding experience since it helped me grow both as a person and academically.	explanations of complex scientific methods used in real-world research. The integration of practical examples and visuals helped me understand how data is collected and validated in atmospheric sciences, which I found very engaging and relevant to my studies.
Quizzes, because they differ to these used in our country.	Flexibility of individual schedule, interview with more specific projects (chambers).
Pedagogical aspect	The general introduction to the RIs.
I particularly enjoyed the interactive quizzes and activities embedded throughout the course. They effectively reinforced the material and allowed me to apply what I learned in real-time. This hands-on approach made the learning experience more engaging and helped solidify my understanding of the concepts.	I particularly enjoyed the parts related to the integration of observational platforms and simulation chambers. They clearly demonstrated how multidisciplinary approaches can strengthen atmospheric research and improve our understanding of complex phenomena.
I want to mention the direct links to the documents, events, and also list of references. All of this is very useful.	The quizzes and case studies on instrumentation and vertical profiling. They helped connect theory to real data and applications.
Graphics were explaining many complicated themed.	IAGOS, because I did not know the project and it has been very interesting for me to know it.
I liked several parts, the first videos, and learning about the different agencies and accessible data.	The interactive parts in the videos.
The first two videos because I'm working in a RI but don't have an atmospheric scientific background.	I liked that each chapter had a transcript and a quiz which helped me see which aspects I missed or didn't pay enough attention to.
I quite liked the sections on research infrastructures. This session gives information about atmospheric monitoring systems and I gained a lot of knowledge about the RIs.	I enjoyed the part about ICOS the most, as my field of research is entangled with ICOS stations.
Introduction to research infrastructures, networks and additional material provided including links to various resources.	Aerosols and clouds, it was very clear and interesting.
The first part about the physical and chemical aspects because it was well synthesized.	The simulation chambers are very interesting
I really liked the interviews with people, describing what they actually do and how they are contributing to the functioning of RIs of how RIs services are useful for their everyday work. Also liked tips from Elena from ICOS to	During this course, I really enjoyed the first week, especially the classes on air pollution and climate change. Thanks to these classes, I was able to gain insights into the study of the atmosphere.

ATMO ACCESS

Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

the younger generations. Also, I liked the links during the videos to other materials.

The content is very structured and the teaching is with a high quality.

The courses during the first week and the quizzes as well because they are useful to validate your knowledge and to fill your gaps.

ACTRIS, ICOS and IAGOS description

I followed the 1st MOOC and I liked the addition with the chambers, good job.

15.2.2 Would you like to add any general remarks?

1 st edition	2 nd edition
Good course to make researchers understand the importance of collaboration and synergies.	It is a fantastic job done by the authors and contributors
Well done!	It has been a great and really useful course, thank you!
Enjoyed the course, thank you.	Awesome course. Good Job!
Great MOOC !!	Great efforts!
I did very much enjoy the course, finding the content both informative and engaging. The structure was clear; topics were well-covered in a concise and lucid manner. I appreciate the opportunity to learn more about such an important and relevant subject. Thank you for offering this educational experience, and I look forward to any future courses you may offer.	Overall, the course was well-structured and informative. The balance between theoretical knowledge and practical applications made it accessible and useful. I appreciate the emphasis on harmonization and collaboration across research infrastructures, which highlights the importance of international cooperation in atmospheric science.
Great effort overall, certainly provides student with useful information in a most easy to comprehend way.	I like very much the content and additional marks with the links of everything to support the knowledge.
Very inspiring and informative course!	Great course for a general overview over everything!
I would like to congratulate for the excellence of ACTRIS, ICOS and IAGOS work and acknowledge for this wonderful MOOC.	I couldn't find if there were any attached slides for each chapter. Otherwise, the course was structured very nicely and I want to revisit the materials, as I am only a beginner.
I would like to congratulate you on the design and content of the course as well as on the excellent preparation of the material provided. I would like them to expand it by developing in depth the contents addressed in this first phase and with a practical approach handling the data from the different atmospheric research infrastructures. My most sincere congratulations to the entire scientific and pedagogical team that has designed and developed this introductory course.	Excellent MOOC. It bridges the gap between technical instrumentation and policy-relevant atmospheric research. Thank you for making it accessible and well-paced.
It was fun and I learn a lot.	I appreciate all that made this course a success.
Thank you so much for this insightful course.	Sometimes the speed was too fast to take notes

16 Appendix: Tutorial videos' open answers

Question: If you have any additional comments or suggestions for topics you'd like to see in future tutorials, please write them below,

Xact
Great video -makes me curious about knowing more of the XACT! Well done. Perfect to watch before a more advanced training. Great with a look inside the instrument and the software for quick looks. Very good that this was shown in Team viewer so that we did not have to listen to the noise. Stuff that I wish to know more about but not necessarily have to be in the video as this may be subject for more advanced training: * A very short overview of the measurement principle (X-ray fluorescence) * Elaborate a bit on the possibility to use it for offline analysis of samples which was mentioned briefly I think? * Could also be good to know what you do in the advanced post-processing of the data and if you need a special program to process the data.
Add some basics on the principles of the instrument. Add some details on air flow rate, calibration method, frequency of maintenance.
Could you provide a training room where users can get hands-on experience with the analysis software and data access, at least for the time period presented in the tutorial? This would allow participants to become familiar with the data and understand how the software works. It could also serve as an effective way to promote both the Xact instrument and the ADAPT analysis software.
TSA
Every new tool released should come with one tutorial like that!
Informative tutorial, thank you! Look and feel of the video could be improved.
A very useful tool for getting a quick idea of the available data. The speaker's accent is very clear, making it easy to follow. It could be mentioned (or shown written) what ACP, APP and AOP specifically refer to. Also, in the info icon of the service webpage, it could be mentioned. *Maybe an icon to enlarge the screen to the entire screen can be added, but it can actually also be done with a zoom, as it is now. Thanks
I have a lot of feedbacks on the applied methodologies and I will give them from the feedback tool of the application. The tutorial is very good.
The video is missing essential information like a link to the tool itself or a link to registration at ORCID. In the introduction part, abbreviations like "RI" are used without explanation. The demonstration of the usage of the tool was good.
Thank you very much. The embedded video was quite small, so I watched the linked video on YouTube instead, but it did not show the link to the tool or at least I did not find it at first attempt.
The video was fine to introduce and explain the tool. In terms of feedback on the content of the tool: I found it restrictive to only be able to select 10 datasets for visualisation and data analysis. I would have wanted to select more. For some of the ACTRIS datasets, e.g. NO ₂ from Hohenpeißenberg and Zugspitze, for one station it was called nitrogen oxides, for the other nitrogen dioxide. For some datasets it was not clear how the datasets differed, e.g. *_1, *_2, *_3 for ACTRIS Hohenpeißenberg g. In terms of units, for CO ₂ data were provided in ppm (umol/mol) and for NO ₂ it was in mass/m ³ . I couldn't see options to change that.
To make the tutorial even more valuable and user-friendly, it could briefly include some scientific context and real-world applications of time series analysis, helping viewers understand why these

methods matter. Adding a short section on methodological details such as basic statistical techniques for trend detection or seasonality—would give users more confidence in applying the tools correctly.

17 Appendix: Serious game's open answers

Question: Add any comments or suggestions below

I was not very convinced by the "run in the dust storm" part ;) but I guess this could appeal to younger players.
For the two matching tests on pages 6, 7 and 15, could we have the number of correct and incorrect answers for the message 'incorrect'?
It would be better to show correct answers throughout the game but otherwise, very interactive, engaging and insightful!
Graphics are cut and dried. Why Max is very 'typical-IT-guy' with this sweatshirt? It might be offensive for some technicians. I had difficulties with understanding the first 'game'.
I think that the Platformer-dream sequence of the game isn't necessary.
Thank you!
Knowing nothing was maybe not a good start. But then I did look at the iPad and that helped.
Better explanations of how to read the graphs. It is clearly the work of someone with a solid understanding of remote sensing. I think this game only works for people with an existing knowledge of aerosols. If you want people without a scientific background to play it you need to modify the game drastically.
Interesting game, needs maybe more details on how to read the graphs. Only theory is given and sometimes there is a gap between understanding the theoretical modeling and the data.
Highlights: I think this is good for students in early stages. One can learn basics of what is important to know. This can make the students interested to dig in further into the filed. I like this.